

Ditransitives in Puma – a Kiranti Language of Eastern Nepal

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Abbreviations

*	ungrammatical (judging an example)
?	odd (judging an example)
1, 2, 3	1 st , 2 nd , 3 rd person
A	agent-like argument
ABL	ablative
ABS	absolutive
ACT	active
ADD	additive
ALL	allative
ANTIP	antipassive
AUX	auxiliary
CAUS	causative
CLF	classifier
CLF(HUM)	classifier for humans
COM	comitative (1)
COM2	comitative 2
CONN	connective
DAT	dative
DEM	demonstrative
ditr.	ditransitive
DOWN.LOC	lower level locative
DU	dual
EMPH	emphatic
ERG	ergative
EXCL	exclusive
EXIST	existential
F	feminine
G	goal-like argument
GEN	genitive
GEN.LOC	general / neutral (level) locative
IMP	imperative
INCL	inclusive

INF	infinitive
IPFV	imperfective
LEVEL.LOC	parallel / same level locative
LOC	locative
M	masculine
NEG	negation
NMLZ	nominalizer
NOM	nominative
NPST	non-past
NSG	non-singular
OBLG	obligatory
P	patient-like argument
PL	plural
POSS	possessive
PRO	pronoun
PROG	progressive
PROX	proximate
PST	past
PTCL	particle
PTCP	participle
R	recipient-like argument
RECP	reciprocal
REFL	reflexive
REP	reportative
S	single argument
SG	singular
T	theme-like argument
TEK	teknonymic
TEL	telic
TOP	topic
tr.	(mono)transitive
UP.LOC	higher level locative
V	verb

VOC

vocative

Σ

verbal stem

Technical Notes

The examples are glossed consistent with the Leipzig Glossing Rules (cf. § *Links* below). The abbreviations follow the Leipzig Glossing Rules and further abbreviations are taken from the *Chintang and Puma Documentation Project's* internal abbreviations list. In some cases there are minor changes, in the glosses of these examples which are not elicited but cited, as for instance SG for formerly s(ingular). When a component of the example is in parenthesis, it is optional, thus may be omitted.

It is indicated, when the examples are cited from other works. When the examples are elicited or from the *Chintang and Puma Documentation Project's* corpus (Chintang and Puma Documentation Project 2008) the reference follows the example in square brackets. The elicited examples have the source shape GKR X.XXX, KKR X.XXX, KR X.XXX, or SKR X.XXX. The initial three (or in one case two) characters refer to my informants, the capital Xs are standing for various numbers here. All references in square brackets which are different from those just mentioned refer to the *Chintang and Puma Documentation Project's* corpus (Chintang and Puma Documentation Project 2008). I did not access the data from the *Chintang and Puma Documentation Project's* corpus deposited at the DoBeS Archive in Nijmegen. Instead, I used the same corpus which is additionally deposited on the internal project server hosted at the University of Leipzig. Furthermore, it is explicitly labeled when the example is from any other language than Puma.

1 Introduction

In this work data and findings on ditransitives in the Southern Kiranti language Puma (ISO 639-3: pum) are presented. On the basis of the *Questionnaire on Ditransitive Constructions* (Comrie et al. 2007) elaborated within the project on *Ditransitive Constructions in the World's Languages I* I consulted native speakers.

My work was possible thanks to my collaboration in the *Chintang and Puma Documentation Project*. It is a cooperation project between the Department of Linguistics at the University of Leipzig and the Central Department of Linguistics located at the Centre for Nepal and Asian Studies at the Tribhuvan University in Kirtipur, Kathmandu, Nepal. The *Chintang and Puma Documentation Project* is a subproject of the DoBeS (Dokumentation Bedrohter Sprachen / Documentation of Endangered Languages) Programme, which is funded by the Volkswagen Foundation (cf. links in the § *Links* below).

The project pursues the linguistic and ethnographic documentation of Chintang and Puma, two highly endangered Kiranti languages of Nepal. Furthermore, the language acquisition of Chintang is being investigated (cf. the homepage of the *Chintang and Puma Documentation Project*; concerning language endangerment in Nepal, cf. as well Toba et al. 2005 and Rai 2005).

The team members working on Puma are Balthasar Bickel, Vishnu Singh Rai, Martin Gaenszle, Judith Pettigrew, Arjun Rai, Ganesh Kumar Rai, Kalpana Rai, Kamala Kumari Rai, Shree Kumar Rai, Narayan P. Sharma (Gautam), Sabine Günther, Diana Schackow, Jenny Seeg, and Taras Zakharko.

During a two months stay in Nepal, I had the opportunity to work within the *Chintang and Puma Documentation Project* partly in the project office located in Kirtipur/Kathmandu, and partly in the project office in Biratnagar (Terai, Eastern Nepal). Unfortunately, due to the tense political situation, it was not possible to reach the Khotang district, where the villages of the Puma Rai people are located. Nevertheless, my stay in Kirtipur and Biratnagar was very productive as I had the opportunity to work together with the Nepalese project members and Puma speaking informants there.

The present work is based on the work already done by the members of the *Chintang and Puma Documentation Project*. During my work on ditransitives in

Puma I had access to the project's *Puma Corpus* (Chintang and Puma Documentation Project 2008), from which I cite several examples and paradigms. Those examples, taken from the *Chintang and Puma Documentation Project's* corpus, are referenced as described above in the section on *Technical Notes*. Moreover, I gathered additional data through eliciting with my informants.

It is important to remark that this work does not claim to be a complete description of ditransitives in Puma, but should be regarded as a first overview of what is found on this topic so far.

In chapter 2 I provide a brief survey of the socio-cultural situation of the Puma Rai people. In chapter 3, a short introduction to the Puma language, its genealogical relation and some grammatical features is given. In chapter 4, I deal with the theoretical issues of ditransitivity. Chapter 5 provides an overview of the existing material on ditransitives in Puma. § 5.1 is about the dative construction. § 5.2 deals with argument encoding properties, § 5.3 gives an account of some behavioral properties of ditransitives in Puma within relative clause formation, focusing, constituent questions, reflexivization, reciprocalization, and antipassive structures. Finally, in chapter 6, a conclusion and outlook is given.

2 The Puma Rai People

The Puma Rai people live in the hills of Eastern Nepal – mainly in the Khotang district in the Sagarmatha zone. The ethnonym *Puma*, meaning ‘jungle’, comes from Camling. The Puma people also name themselves *Rakoŋ*, as well meaning ‘jungle’.

Speaking about the group of Kiranti people, to which the Rai people belong, van Driem (2001: 590 ff.) states that the Kirantis were a ruling dynasty in the Kathmandu Valley for nearly two thousand years during the first millennium BC and the first millennium AD. Nowadays, the Kiranti people live in Eastern Nepal in the hilly Himalayan region between the Dūdhkosī and the Aruṅ rivers. The Kiranti people are a subgroup of the Tibeto-Burman people encompassing the ethnic communities of the Rāī and the Limbū. Already before Pṛthvī Nārāyaṇ Śāh’s Gorkhā conquest in the end of the 1760s, which lead to the founding of Nepal, the term Kirānt(ī) was used “to denote both a specific ethnolinguistic and geographical concept” (van Driem 2001: 596), referring to the people living in the area which is nowadays Eastern Nepal. In 1776, in the Battle of Cainpur the Gorkhālī government started after all to conquer also the Kiranti area (ibid.: 603). Besides, in the 1930s the term Kiranti was used in a broader sense to refer to “any non-Indo-Aryan tribal people” (ibid.: 597).

The Rai and Limbu people were “rural agriculturalists” in the hills of today’s Eastern Nepal (cf. ibid.: 599). But the Limbu and the Yakkha people tell themselves apart from the “remaining Kiranti groups, who are known collectively as [...] Rāī” (ibid.: 602).

van Driem (2001: 614) provides two alternative explanations for the Nepali term *Rāī*. One approach declares that the term was used to entitle a “rank officer in the revenue collection system”. The term is said to derive from “the Karṇālī region in western Nepal, where it designated a local chieftain.” The second explanation, van Driem provides, is that the term *Rāī*, as a “collective designation for Central and Western Kiranti groups, [...] has a local Kiranti etymology.” There is a high evidence for assuming Kiranti etymology, as the Nepali term *Rāī* is very similar to “names by which various Rai tribes refer to themselves, for example Dumi *ɾəʔd̪i*, Ombule *ɾa:ɽu* and Chamling ‘Ródóng’.” (ibid.: 614) As already noted above the Puma people use such autonym as *Rakoŋ*,

referring to themselves, or *rokuŋla* or *rokoŋla* (*la* 'language'), referring to their language (cf. Bickel et al. 2005a: 1).

Already in former times the Kiranti people had their own religion. They were “shamanists practising an indigenous Himalayan form of animism”. Up to today, they maintained these practices, even if the influence of the Hindi religion grows. Nevertheless, one has to distinguish between the Limbu’s and the Rai’s religious practices (van Driem 2001: 605).

3 The Puma Language

Before the *Chintang and Puma Documentation Project* started to work on these two Kiranti languages, the Puma language was, except for some initial research by Novel Kishore Rai and Madhav Pokharel (both from Tribhuvan University), totally undocumented (cf. Bickel et al. 2005a: 2). On other Kiranti languages there has been done descriptive research. Nowadays, there are a few linguistic and ethnological studies available inter alia on Athpare (Ebert 1997b), Bantawa (Rai 1985), Belhare (Bickel 1996; 2004), Camling (Ebert 1997a), and Limbu (van Driem 1987).

Puma is spoken in the hills of Eastern Nepal – mainly in the Khotang and Udaypur districts in the Sagarmatha zone in South-Eastern Nepal (cf. Figure 1). The Puma people are surrounded by the Bantawa people to the east and by Chamling people on to the west. The language is highly influenced by Nepali (lingua franca in Nepal) and Bantawa. Most of the speakers are multilingual. Like many other indigenous languages, Puma is highly endangered.

The official number of Puma speakers is 4310 (Central Bureau of Statistics 2001). However, the Puma people who live in the Khotang district declare that there are about 10.000 people speaking the language Puma. Other estimations amount to more than 6.000 native speakers of Puma (cf. Bickel et al. 2005a: 1). Thus, the Puma people are a small group and their language tends to disappear (cf. van Driem 2001).

In the map in Figure 1, it is marked where the Kiranti languages Puma and Chintang are mainly spoken. In the “area between the Arun and the Likhu rivers” not only Puma is spoken but also other Central Kiranti languages such as Bantawa and Chamling (Camling) (cf. van Driem 2001: 603).

Figure 1. Map of the area where Puma and Chintang are mainly spoken (source: <http://www.uni-leipzig.de/~ff/cdpd/>)

3.1 Genealogical Relation

The Kiranti language Puma belongs to the Tibeto-Burman language family (Tibeto-Burman > Kiranti > Central-Eastern > Central > Southern > Puma (cf. Figure 2)), and is very closely related to Chamling. According to Ebert (1994: 9) there are about 30 Kiranti languages.

Figure 2. Tree of the Genealogical Relation of the Kiranti Languages (source: <http://www.uni-leipzig.de/~ff/cpdp/>)

Puma is genealogical most closely related to Chamling, as one finds similar linguistic innovations. A striking feature is the “voicing of preglottalized initials and merger of the back and front rhotics”. This encourages the classification of Puma as Southern Central Kiranti language. The following examples illustrate this feature: “in agreement with van Driem 2001; cf., for example, Puma *buywa* ‘flower’, *bok* ‘pig’, *duŋ-* ‘drink’, *dem* ‘how, what’, all from stems with preglottalized initials; and *rum* ‘salt’, *ram* ‘body’, *rom-t-* ‘weak’, *ri-* ‘laugh’ all from stems with initial < **r-* ; vs. *ruks-* ‘shake’, *rok-oŋ* ‘Puma’ etc. from stems with < **r->* .” (Bickel et al. 2005a: 1 f.)

3.2 Some Basic Facts on the Puma Grammar

In general, one can say about Kiranti languages that they have a very complex morphology which is not very transparent. Comparing the Kiranti languages, Puma is said to have a “richer and more complex verbal morphology than Bantawa.” (van Driem 2001: 710).

As it is very common among the Kiranti languages (cf. van Driem 2001: 629), the pronominal system of Puma includes 10 personal pronouns, distinguishing between 1st, 2nd and 3rd person, in singular, dual and plural number, and in the 1st person dual and plural between inclusive and exclusive (cf. § 3.2.1). Pronouns can be dropped. Nouns and pronouns distinguish ten cases - nominative, ergative/instrumental, dative, genitive, locative, ablative, allative, comitative 1, comitative 2, and vocative.

As among the Kiranti languages a rich inventory of “lexical and grammatical categories which express spatial deixis” are a widespread phenomenon (cf. van Driem 2001: 660), in Puma spatial deixis is expressed through the four different forms or the locative case (cf. § 3.2.2). Moreover, spatial deixis is expressed through demonstratives and even more differentiated adverbs.

The basic word order is SOV. Due to information structure, variation is possible. Within the noun phrase the order is strictly head-final.

Also verbal agreement is rather complex. In the verbal morphology a distinction is drawn between past and non-past tense. The verb agrees not only with the S and A argument, but also with the P argument, what is rare among the languages of the world. As stated by Bickel et al. (2005b), this typologically

rare phenomenon is characteristic for the Kiranti languages. A is understood here as the Agent-like argument of a mono- or ditransitive clause/verb. P is understood as the Patient-like argument. Bickel et al. (2005b) point out that the verbal agreement shows split alignment. Besides, verbal agreement distinguishes between singular, dual and plural arguments (cf. § 3.2.3). A special feature in the languages in South Asia are compound verbs (cf. § 3.2.4).

Interestingly there are two kinds of antipassive-like constructions (cf. § 5.3.6) (Bickel et al. 2007).

3.2.1 Personal and Possessive Pronouns

As described by Bickel et al. (2005a), Puma pronouns distinguish between 1st, 2nd and 3rd person pronouns in singular, dual and plural number. In the 1st person dual and plural one, furthermore, distinguishes between inclusive and exclusive. Table 1 gives an overview of Puma personal pronouns and possessive markers.

	Nominative		Genitive
	Personal Pronoun	Possessive marker	
1SG	<i>ŋa</i>	<i>uŋ-</i>	<i>uŋ-bo</i>
1DU.INCL	<i>keci</i>	<i>enci-</i>	<i>enci-bo</i>
1PL.INCL	<i>ke</i>	<i>en-</i>	<i>en-bo</i>
1DU.EXCL	<i>keci(ʌ)ka</i>	<i>aci-</i>	<i>aci-bo</i>
1PL.EXCL	<i>keka</i>	<i>a-</i>	<i>a-bo</i>
2SG	<i>khanna</i>	<i>ka-</i>	<i>ka-bo</i>
2DU	<i>khannaci</i>	<i>kenci-</i>	<i>kenci-bo</i>
2PL	<i>khannanin</i>	<i>ken-</i>	<i>ken-bo</i>
3SG	<i>kho(kku)</i>	<i>kʌ-</i>	<i>kho(kku)-bo</i>
3NSG	<i>kho(kku)ci</i>	<i>kʌci-</i>	<i>khoci-bo</i>

Table 1. Personal pronouns and possessive markers in Puma (Bickel et al. 2005a: 6; slightly changed)

In the 1st person personal pronouns *-ci* marks the dual, *-ka* marks the exclusive. Like in the Eastern Kiranti language Belhare there is no overt inclusive marker (cf. Bickel & Nichols 2007: 221).

The 1st person plural is in a non-dual non-singular form. Also on 2nd person pronouns dual is marked by the suffix *-ci*, but in contrast to the situation with the 1st person pronouns there is no stem variation. “As a result, the plural is indicated not by a zero morpheme, but by a specific suffix, *-nin*.” (Bickel et al. 2005a: 4). In the 3rd person *-ci* marks the non-singular. In this case, disambiguation between dual and plural happens through adding a numeral (cf. example (2)), or through verbal agreement. Bickel et al. (2005a: 4) point out that “a dual/nonsingular homophony [...] is widespread in Kiranti languages.”

As one can see in example (1), possessives occur as prefixes and may also appear as possessive pronouns, suffixed by the genitive. That is true except for the 3rd person, where genitive marking is impossible. In this case, the genitive appears on the personal pronoun instead (cf. ex. (2), where, furthermore, the disambiguation between dual and plural through the adding a numeral is shown).

(1) (Bickel et al. 2005a: 7)

<i>ka-bo</i>	<i>ka-khim</i>
2SG.POSS-GEN	2SG.POSS-house
‘your (SG) house’	

(2) (Bickel et al. 2005a: 6)

<i>khokku-ci-bo</i>	<i>ʌʌ-poŋ</i>	<i>kʌci-khim</i>
3SG-DU-GEN	two-CLF(HUM)	3DU.POSS-house
‘their (dual) house’		

3.2.2 Case Markers

Sharma (2005) overviews the ten case markers one finds in the Puma language. They are nominative, ergative, dative, genitive, locative, ablative, allative, comitative 1, comitative 2, and vocative cases. The following table summarizes the morphological forms of the individual cases.

	Form	Use
Nominative (NOM)	$[-\emptyset]$	S, P arguments (optional), T
Ergative (ERG)	<i>-a</i>	A arguments, (Instrument)
Dative (DAT)	<i>-lai</i>	P (optional), R arguments
Genitive (GEN)	<i>-bo</i>	possession
Locative	<i>-do</i>	neutral/general level
(GEN.LOC)	<i>-ya</i>	parallel/same level
(LEVEL.LOC)	<i>-di</i>	higher level
(UP.LOC)	<i>-i</i>	lower level
(DOWN.LOC)		
Ablative (ABL)	$(-LOC)-\eta k o \eta$	movement ‘away from’
Allative (ALL)	$(-LOC)-t n i$	movement ‘towards’
Comitative 1 (COM)	<i>-o \eta</i>	RECP As
Comitative 2 (COM2)	<i>-p \lambda (-LOC)</i>	possession and contact
	<i>-p \lambda d o</i>	+ neutral level; R
	<i>-p \lambda y a</i>	+ parallel level
	<i>-p \lambda d i</i>	+ higher level
	<i>-p \lambda i</i>	+ lower level
Vocative (VOC)	<i>-o</i> (or <i>-\lambda i</i>)	addressing

Table 2. Cases in Puma (based on Sharma 2005)

The unmarked **nominative** case is used for marking the S and (optionally) the P argument when the P argument does not bear the dative case *-lai* (cf. Sharma 2005: 1 f.). Furthermore, the nominative case marks T arguments of a ditransitive verb. One might call the unmarked case absolutive, but following Bickel & Nichols’ (2009: 304) argumentation, the term nominative is more appropriate for Puma, since not only S and P arguments may be marked by the unmarked $-\emptyset$ case, but also A arguments (of antipassivized verbs). In the intransitive example (3), the S argument is in the nominative case. In the monotransitive example (4), the A argument is marked by the ergative suffix *-a*, the P argument is marked by the dative case *-lai* or unflagged / marked by the $-\emptyset$ marker for the nominative case respectively. In the ditransitive example (5), the A argument is marked by the ergative suffix *-a*, the R argument is (obligatorily) marked by the dative suffix *-lai*, and the T argument remains unmarked.

example (8) show an ergatively flagged A argument. Example (9) demonstrates the ergative/instrumental case in the instrumental use.

- (8) *khanna-a* *ŋa-lai* *ʌk-ta* *kitaba[-∅]* *tʌ-itd-oŋ.*
 2SG-ERG 1SG-DAT one-CLF book[-NOM] 2-give-
 1SG.R.PST
 ‘You gave me a book.’ [GKR 6.002]
- (9) *ɾʌŋ* *hʌk-ma-ci-dot* *ʌthʌwa* *wapa-a* *ʌthʌwa*
 CONN ritually.purify-INF-NSG-OBLG or rooster-ERG or
wama-a.
 hen-ERG
 ‘... and then purification has to be done, either with a rooster or a hen.
 (The rooster or hen is used for the purpose of purification.)’
 [DA_marry_02.118]

The **dative** case suffix *-lai* marks the P argument of a monotransitive verb (cf. example (7) a. above) and the R argument of a ditransitive verb (cf. example (8) above) respectively. With the P argument *-lai* is optional, but in some cases obligatory, that is when the argument is specific. The T argument of a ditransitive verb never bears the dative case (cf. Sharma 2005: 2 ff.).

Ebert (1994: 82) states that the dative suffix *-lai* in Kiranti languages might be borrowed from the Nepali dative *-lāi*. On the other hand, she mentions a Tibeto-Burman dative marker *-la*. Thus, the etymology of the Kiranti dative *-lai* remains unclear.

The **genitive** suffix *-bo* serves to indicate possession or a relation between the head noun and its modifier, as one sees in example (10).

- (10) (Sharma 2005: 3)
uŋ-bo *uŋ-marchacha-bo* *kʌ-nʌŋ* *dipti*
 1SG.POSS-GEN 1SG.POSS-daughter-GEN 3SG.POSS-name a_name
 ‘My daughter's name is Deepti.’

There are four **locative** case markers used for the specification of the location relative to the speaker. Among the Kiranti speakers north counts as the higher level, south is observed as the lower level, and east and west count as parallel or same level (cf. Sharma 2005: 4 ff.). In example (11) the road is flagged by the general locative case suffix.

(11) (Sharma 2005: 4; [myth_02.60])

lam-do *tup-ma* *pee*
road-GEN.LOC meet-INF NEG

‘There was no one to meet on the road.’

The **ablative** case suffix *-ŋkoŋ* serves for expressing “ ‘out of’ or ‘away from’ or the place from which something moves” (Sharma 2005: 5). The ablative case marker can be combined with any of the locative case markers, to which it is attached then. Thus, the meaning is extended to levels of location (cf. Sharma 2005: 5). Example (12) shows such a case compound. On the first constituent, only the plain ablative case marker *-ŋkoŋ* is used, whereas on the last constituent it is combined with the higher level locative marker *-di*, which precedes the ablative marker.

(12) (Sharma 2005: 5; [convers_002.a])

kharo-ŋkoŋ *daju[-Ø]* *khim-diŋkoŋ*.
where-ABL elder.brother[-NOM] house-UP.ABL

‘Brother, from where? From the house?’

Like the ablative case, the **allative** case *-tni* can be combined with the locative case markers which precede the allative marker. In the following example (13) one sees how the case compound, consisting of the same level locative *-ya* and the allative *-tni*, “expresses a notion of ‘to’ or ‘towards’ a place” (Sharma 2005: 6).

(13) (Sharma 2005: 6; [myth_orph_01.046])

toŋwama[-Ø] *purbΛ-yatni* *puks-a* *rachΛ*.
a_person[-NOM] east-LEVEL.ALL go-PST MIR

‘Tongwama went towards east.’

The **comitative 1** case *-oŋ* marks an association with someone. It only can appear on animate arguments, as shown in example (14) (cf. Sharma 2005: 6).

(14) (Sharma 2005: 6; [senti_song_01.13])

nimna-ci-oŋ *men-pi-d-a*.
other-NSG-COM NEG-speak-TEL-IMP

‘Don't speak with others!’

The **comitative 2** case¹ *-pɿ* is, like the ablative and allative cases, combined with the locative case markers. Thus, the comitative 2 indicates the relation to the location of the speaker. But unlike the ablative and allative cases the comitative 2 case precedes the locative case marker. So the order is reversed. The comitative 2 serves as marker of “possession of something and contact with someone”. It is important to note that “the person mustn't be there with the speaker at the time of speaking” (Sharma 2005: 6). In the following example (15) a., the speaker is in contact with the queen whereas the queen must not be with the speaker at the time of speaking. In (15) b., there is a possessive relationship between the speaker and the money at the time of speaking (cf. Sharma 2005: 7).

- (15) (Sharma 2005: 7)
- a. *ŋa-pɿya/-pɿdi/-pɿi* *hoŋma[-∅]* *yurɿyaŋ*.
 1SG-COM2 queen[-NOM] NPST.EXIST
 ‘I have the queen (but she isn't here with me).’
- b. *ŋa-pɿya/-pɿdi/-pɿi* *kaɸhekwa[-∅]* *yurɿyaŋ*
 1SG-COM2 money[-NOM] NPST.EXIST
 ‘I have money.’

Examples (16) a - c demonstrate the difference in usage of comitative 1 and comitative 2. In (16) a. the comitative 1 is used for expressing the alliance with a person. The ungrammatical example in (16) b. shows that such a personal alliance cannot be expressed with the comitative 2 case. Whereas, in (16) c. the comitative 2 possession is expressed.

- (16) (Balthasar Bickel, p.c., elicited with Kamala Kumari Rai & Shree Kumar Rai)
- a. *Ganesh-oŋ* *Prem[-∅]* *yurɿyaŋ*
 a_person-COM1 a_person[-NOM] NPST.EXIST
 ‘Prem is with Ganesh.’
- b. **Ganesh-pɿdo* *Prem[-∅]* *yurɿyaŋ*
 a_person-COM2 a_person[-NOM] NPST.EXIST
Intended: ‘Prem is with Ganesh.’

¹ Which yet seems not to be found in other Kiranti languages.

- c. *Ganesh-pado* *palisa[-Ø]* *yuyyaŋ*
 a_person-COM2 money[-NOM] NPST.EXIST
 ‘With Ganesh is money.’ (‘Ganesh has money.’)

The **vocative** case marker *-o*, or *-li* respectively, is used when addressing someone. In the following example (17) ‘elder sister’ bears the vocative case (cf. Sharma 2005: 7 f.).

- (17) (Sharma 2005: 7; [folk_tale_01.020])
*nano*² *sokwama[-Ø]* *li-yaŋ*
 elder.sister.VOC hunger[-NOM] be-IPFV.NPST
 ‘Sister! I got hungry.’

3.2.3 Verbal Morphology

In Puma, some verbs show stem alternations (cf. Stutz 2005). The augment *-d* appears in the prevocalic position (cf. Bickel et al. 2007). There are augments which change the meaning of a verb. (e.g. *dungma* ‘drink’ vs. *dukma* ‘feed liquid’; *benma* ‘come.level’ vs. *betma* ‘bring.level’; *tama* ‘come’ vs. *tatma* ‘bring’). One example for an augment that does not change the meaning is the verb *itma* ‘give’. Compare, for instance, the non-past forms *itd-i* (give-3P) and *it-na* (give-1SG>2). *itdi* is zero marked for the 3rd person singular A argument and overtly marked for the 3rd person (singular) P argument, and, as the agreement suffix is a vowel, bears the stem alternating augment *d*. *itna* bears the portmanteau morpheme suffix *-na* indicating the 1st person singular acting on a 2nd person (in this case singular, as no dual or plural suffix is attached). As the suffix begins with a consonant, the verb does not undergo any stem alternation.

The system of verbal agreement is very rich in Puma. In transitive forms the A as well as the P arguments are indexed on the verb. It is distinguished between three numbers (singular, dual and plural), three persons (1st, 2nd and 3rd), and in the 1st person non-singular forms it is, furthermore, distinguished between inclusive and exclusive. In Table 4 and Table 5 one finds the non-past and past paradigms of the verb *imma* ‘sleep’. In Table 6 and Table 7 the non-past and past paradigms of the verb *itma* ‘give’ are provided. Moreover, negation is marked on the verb. I do not provide any further details about negation here, as

² *nana-o* > *nano* (elder.sister-VOC > elder.sister.VOC)

this is not in the focus of the present work. What is not dealt with but should be mentioned is verbal marking for the imperfective aspect³.

As with the pronouns (cf. § 3.2.1) in the verbal agreement the 3rd person -*ci* (~-cɿ) suffix marks the non-singular. As Bickel et al. (2005a: 4) point out (while dealing with pronouns) “a dual/nonsingular homophony [...] is widespread in Kiranti languages”. For example the suffix -*ci* (~-cɿ) may mark dual or non-singular. In some cases, disambiguation is possible by considering the whole verb form. In other cases, disambiguation may happen through numerals. Stutz (2005) states that the dual prefix -*ci* (~-cɿ) is neutral with regard to person, tense and speech act participants, thus it marks virtually all persons and arguments (when they are indexed on the verb). This seems to be very common among the Kiranti language (cf. as well van Driem 1993).

The verbal agreement system shows traits of a split-ergativity. In Table 3 on alignment in agreement, one finds the affixes which are relevant for indexing the A, S, P, and R arguments on the verb. Here, it is already assumed that T arguments are not marked on the verb. Bickel et al. (2005b) point out that the verbal agreement shows split alignment. There is “ergative alignment with 1SG but not further down the referential hierarchy” (Bickel et al. 2005b). As one sees in Table 3, the 1st person marks the A argument differently from the S, P and R arguments. For the 2nd person there is one marker, indexing the A as well as the S, the P, and the R argument on the verb. In the dual number there is not either distinguished, whether the A, S, P, or R argument is indexed on the verb. In the 3rd person singular and plural respectively, the A and the S arguments are indexed on the verb with the same markers, differently from the indexing of the P and R arguments.

³ For a detailed affix analysis of the Puma conjugation system see Stutz 2005.

Non Past (illustrated by <i>imma</i> , <i>im-</i> and <i>ips-</i> ‘sleep’)				
Researcher: Narayan P Sharma (Gautam)				
Informant: Prem Dhoj Rai				
Location: Beltar				
Pronouns	NPST	NPST.NEG	NPST.PROG	NPST.PROG.NEG
1SG <i>ḡa</i>	<i>imḡa</i>	<i>ṛaimnḡa</i>	<i>imḡaḡa</i>	<i>ṛaimnḡaḡa</i>
1DU.INCL <i>keci</i>	<i>imci</i>	<i>ṛaimcamin</i>	<i>imcaḡci</i>	<i>ṛaimcaḡcamin</i>
1PL.INCL <i>ke</i>	<i>ipse</i>	<i>ṛaipṣamin</i>	<i>ipsaḡi</i>	<i>ṛaipṣaḡḡamin</i>
1DU.EXCL <i>kecika</i>	<i>imcika</i>	<i>ṛaimcaminḡa</i>	<i>imcaḡcika</i>	<i>ṛaimcaḡcaminḡa</i>
1PL.EXCL <i>keka</i>	<i>ipseka</i>	<i>ṛaipṣaminḡa</i>	<i>ipseḡka</i>	<i>ṛaipṣeḡḡaminḡa</i>
2SG <i>khanna</i>	<i>ṭaim</i>	<i>ṭaimnin</i>	<i>ṭaimyaḡ</i>	<i>ṭaimninyan</i>
2DU <i>khannaci</i>	<i>ṭaimci</i>	<i>ṭaimcamin</i>	<i>ṭaimcaḡi</i>	<i>ṭaimcaḡcamin</i>
2PL <i>khannanin</i>	<i>ṭaipse</i>	<i>ṭaipṣemin</i>	<i>ṭaipṣaḡi</i>	<i>ṭaipṣaḡḡamin</i>
3SG <i>khokku</i>	<i>im</i>	<i>ṛaimnim</i>	<i>imyaḡ</i>	<i>ṛaimninyan</i>
3DU <i>khoci</i>	<i>ṛaimci</i>	<i>ṛaimcamin</i>	<i>ṛaimcaḡci</i>	<i>ṛaimcaḡcamin</i>
3PL <i>khoci</i>	<i>mṭaim</i>	<i>nṛaimnin</i>	<i>mṭaimyaḡ</i>	<i>nṛaimninyan</i>

Table 4. Intransitive paradigm (non-past) of imma ‘sleep’. (Chintang and Puma Documentation Project 2008)

Past (illustrated by <i>imma</i> , <i>im-</i> and <i>ips-</i> ‘sleep’)				
Researcher: Narayan P Sharma (Gautam)				
Informant: Prem Dhoj Rai				
Location: Beltar				
Pronouns	PST	PST.NEG	PST.PROG	PST.PROG.NEG
1SG <i>ḡa</i>	<i>ipsḡ</i>	<i>ṛaimnḡa</i>	<i>ipsḡyaḡ</i>	<i>ṛaimnḡaḡa</i>
1DU.INCL <i>keci</i>	<i>ipsaci</i>	<i>ṛaipṣacamin</i>	<i>ipsaḡci</i>	<i>ṛaipṣaḡcamin</i>
1PL.INCL <i>ke</i>	<i>ipsanin</i>	<i>ṛaipṣanamin</i>	<i>ipsaḡin</i>	<i>ṛaipṣaḡḡamin</i>
1DU.EXCL <i>kecika</i>	<i>ipsacika</i>	<i>ṛaipṣaminḡa</i>	<i>ipsaḡcika</i>	<i>ṛaipṣaḡcaminḡa</i>
1PL.EXCL <i>keka</i>	<i>ipsaninḡa</i>	<i>ṛaipṣanaminḡa</i>	<i>ipsaḡinḡa</i>	<i>ṛaipṣaḡḡaminḡa</i>
2SG <i>khanna</i>	<i>ṭaipṣa</i>	<i>ṭaipṣen</i>	<i>ṭaipṣaḡa</i>	<i>ṭaipṣenyan</i>
2DU <i>khannaci</i>	<i>ṭaipṣaci</i>	<i>ṭaipṣacamin</i>	<i>ṭaipṣaḡci</i>	<i>ṭaipṣaḡcamin</i>
2PL <i>khannanin</i>	<i>ṭaipṣanin</i>	<i>ṭaipṣanamin</i>	<i>ṭaipṣaḡnin</i>	<i>ṭaipṣaḡḡamin</i>
3SG <i>khokku</i>	<i>ipsa</i>	<i>ṛaipṣen</i>	<i>ipsaḡa</i>	<i>ṛaipṣenyan</i>
3DU <i>khoci</i>	<i>ṛaipṣaci</i>	<i>ṛaipṣacamin</i>	<i>ṛaipṣaḡci</i>	<i>ṛaipṣaḡcamin</i>
3PL <i>khoci</i>	<i>mṭaipṣa</i>	<i>nṛaipṣen</i>	<i>mṭaipṣaḡa</i>	<i>nṛaipṣenyan</i>

Table 5. Intransitive paradigm (past) of imma ‘sleep’. (Chintang and Puma Documentation Project 2008)

Illustrated by **NonPast (itma 'give')**
 Researcher: Narayan Gautam
 Informant: Prem Dhoj Rai
 Space: Beltar

Simple nontensed augmented stem: CV(C)-T -->CV(C) before C; Subtype CVC-d (never CVct-)

	1SG	1DU.INCL	1PL.INCL	1DU.EXCL	1PL.EXCL	2SG	2DU	2PL	3SG	3NSG	ANTIPASSIVE
1SG						<i>itna</i>	<i>itnaci</i>	<i>itnanin</i>	<i>itduj</i>	<i>itdujcaɣ</i>	<i>khaitja</i>
1DU.INCL						<i>ɣaitnen</i>	<i>ɣaitnacimin</i>	<i>ɣaitnanimin</i>	<i>ɣaitnaɣ</i>	<i>ɣaitnaɣcaɣ</i>	<i>khaitci</i>
1PL.INCL						<i>itdum</i>	<i>itdumcam</i>	<i>khaitdi</i>			
1DU.EXCL						<i>ɣaitdummin</i>	<i>ɣaitdumcammin</i>	<i>khapaitdimin</i>			
1PL.EXCL						<i>nitaɪt</i>	<i>nitaɪtci</i>	<i>nitaɪtdi</i>	<i>itcika</i>	<i>itcicika</i>	<i>khaitcika</i>
				<i>nitaɪtnin</i>	<i>nitaɪtcimin</i>	<i>nitaɪtdimin</i>	<i>ɣaitciminka</i>	<i>ɣaitciciminka</i>	<i>khapaitciminka</i>		
					<i>nitaɪtdi</i>	<i>nitaɪtdimin</i>	<i>itdumka</i>	<i>itdumcamka</i>	<i>khaitdika</i>		
							<i>ɣaitdumminka</i>	<i>ɣaitdumcamminka</i>	<i>khapaitdiminka</i>		
2SG	<i>taɪtja</i>			<i>khataɪt</i>				<i>taɪtdi</i>	<i>taɪtdici</i>	<i>khataɪt</i>	
	<i>taɪtnaɣ</i>			<i>khataɪtnin</i>				<i>taɪtdin</i>	<i>taɪtdicin</i>	<i>khataɪtnin</i>	
2DU	<i>taɪtjaɣaɣ</i>			<i>khataɪtci</i>				<i>taɪtci</i>	<i>taɪtcici</i>	<i>khataɪtci</i>	
	<i>taɪtnaɣcamɣ</i>	<i>khataɪtcimin</i>	<i>taɪtcimin</i>	<i>taɪtcicimin</i>	<i>khataɪtcimin</i>						
2PL	<i>taɪtjanɣ</i>			<i>khataɪtdi</i>	<i>taɪtdum</i>	<i>taɪtdumcam</i>	<i>khataɪtdi</i>				
	<i>taɪtnaɣnamɣ</i>			<i>khataɪtdimin</i>	<i>taɪtdummin</i>	<i>taɪtdumcammin</i>	<i>khataɪtdimin</i>				
3SG	<i>ɣaitja</i>	<i>khait</i>	<i>ɣaitcika</i>	<i>ɣaitdika</i>	<i>taɪt</i>	<i>taɪtci</i>	<i>taɪtdi</i>	<i>itdi</i>	<i>itdici</i>	<i>khait</i>	
	<i>ɣaitnaɣ</i>	<i>khapaitnin</i>	<i>ɣaitciminka</i>	<i>ɣaitdiminka</i>	<i>taɪtnin</i>	<i>taɪtcimin</i>	<i>taɪtdimin</i>	<i>ɣaitdin</i>	<i>ɣaitdincin</i>	<i>khapaitnin</i>	
3DU	<i>ɣaitjaɣaɣ</i>	<i>khapaitci</i>	<i>nipaitcika</i>		<i>nitaɪt</i>	<i>nitaɪtci</i>	<i>nitaɪtdi</i>	<i>ɣaitci</i>	<i>ɣaitcici</i>	<i>khapaitci</i>	
	<i>ɣaitnaɣcamɣ</i>	<i>khapaitcimin</i>	<i>nipaitciminka</i>		<i>nitaɪtnin</i>	<i>nitaɪtcimin</i>		<i>ɣaitcimin</i>	<i>ɣaitcicimin</i>	<i>khapaitcimin</i>	
3PL	<i>nipaitja</i>	<i>khamait</i>	<i>nipaitdika</i>		<i>nitaɪtnin</i>	<i>nitaɪtdi</i>	<i>nitaɪtdimin</i>	<i>ɣait</i>	<i>maitdici</i>	<i>khamait</i>	
	<i>nipaitnaɣ</i>	<i>khanipaitnin</i>	<i>nipaitdiminka</i>			<i>nitaɪtdimin</i>		<i>nipaitdin</i>	<i>nipaitdincin</i>	<i>khanipaitnin</i>	

Table 6. Transitive paradigm (non-past) of *itma* 'give'. Within the paradigm table, the upper cases refer to affirmative and the lower cases refer to negative. (Chintang and Puma Documentation Project 2008)

Illustrated by **Past (itma 'give')**
 Researcher: Narayan Gautam
 Informant: Prem Dhoj Rai
 Space: Beltar

Simple nontensed augmented stem: CV(C)-T -->CV(C) before C; Subtype CVC-d (never CVct-)

	1SG	1DU.INCL	1PL.INCL	1DU.EXCL	1PL.EXCL	2SG	2DU	2PL	3SG	3NSG	ANTIPASSIVE			
1SG						<i>itnaa</i>	<i>itnaaci</i>	<i>itnaanin</i>	<i>itduuy</i>	<i>itduuycaɣ</i>	<i>khaitdoɣ</i>			
1DU.INCL									<i>ɣaitneen</i>	<i>ɣaitnaacimin</i>	<i>ɣaitnaanimin</i>	<i>ɣaitnɔɣ</i>	<i>ɣaitnɔɣcaɣ</i>	<i>kharɣaitnɔɣ</i>
1PL.INCL									<i>itdaci</i>	<i>itdacici</i>	<i>khaitdaci</i>			
1DU.EXCL						<i>itduum</i>	<i>itduumcam</i>	<i>khaitdanin</i>						
1PL.EXCL						<i>ɣaitduummin</i>	<i>ɣaitduumcammin</i>	<i>kharɣaitdanimin</i>						
						<i>nitaitda</i>	<i>nitaitdaci</i>	<i>nitaitdanin</i>	<i>itdacika</i>	<i>itdacicika</i>	<i>khaitdacika</i>			
						<i>nitaitden</i>	<i>nitaitdacimin</i>	<i>nitaitdanimin</i>	<i>ɣaitdaciminka</i>	<i>ɣaitdaciciminka</i>	<i>kharɣaitdaciminka</i>			
									<i>itduumka</i>	<i>itduumcamka</i>	<i>khaitdaninka</i>			
									<i>ɣaitduumminka</i>	<i>ɣaitduumcamminka</i>	<i>kharɣaitdaniminka</i>			
2SG	<i>taɪtoɣ</i>			<i>khataitda</i>				<i>taɪtdii</i>	<i>taɪtdici</i>	<i>khatait</i>				
	<i>taɪtnɔɣ</i>			<i>khataitden</i>				<i>taɪtdiin</i>	<i>taɪtdincin</i>	<i>khataitnin</i>				
2DU	<i>taɪtdoɣcaɣ</i>			<i>khataitdaci</i>				<i>taɪtdaci</i>	<i>taɪtdacimin</i>	<i>khataitci</i>				
	<i>taɪtnɔɣcamɔɣ</i>	<i>khataitdacimin</i>	<i>taɪtdaciminka</i>	<i>taɪtdaciminka</i>	<i>khataitcimin</i>									
2PL	<i>taɪtdoɣnɔɣ</i>	<i>khataitdanin</i>	<i>taɪtduum</i>	<i>taɪtdumcam</i>	<i>khataitdi</i>									
	<i>taɪtnɔɣnamɔɣ</i>	<i>khataitdanimin</i>	<i>taɪtduummin</i>	<i>taɪtdumcammin</i>	<i>khataitdimin</i>									
3SG	<i>ɣaitdoɣ</i>	<i>khaitda</i>	<i>ɣaitdacika</i>	<i>ɣaitddaninka</i>	<i>taɪtda</i>	<i>taɪtdaci</i>	<i>taɪtdanin</i>	<i>itdii</i>	<i>itdici</i>	<i>khait</i>				
	<i>ɣaitnɔɣ</i>	<i>kharɣaitden</i>	<i>ɣaitdaciminka</i>	<i>ɣaitdaniminka</i>	<i>taɪtden</i>	<i>taɪtdacimin</i>	<i>taɪtdanimin</i>	<i>ɣaitdiin</i>	<i>ɣaitdincin</i>	<i>kharɣaitnin</i>				
3DU	<i>ɣaitdoɣcaɣ</i>	<i>kharɣaitdaci</i>	<i>nɪɣaitdacika</i>	<i>nɪɣaitdaciminka</i>	<i>nitaitda</i>	<i>nitaitdaci</i>	<i>nitaitdanin</i>	<i>ɣaitdaci*</i>	<i>ɣaitcici</i>	<i>kharɣaitci</i>				
	<i>ɣaitnɔɣcamɔɣ</i>	<i>kharɣaitdacimin</i>	<i>nɪɣaitdaciminka</i>		<i>nitaitden</i>	<i>nitaitdacimin</i>	<i>nitaitdanimin</i>	<i>ɣaitdacimin</i>	<i>ɣaitcicimin</i>	<i>kharɣaitcimin</i>				
3PL	<i>nɪɣaitdoɣ</i>	<i>khamaitda</i>	<i>nɪɣaitdaninka</i>			<i>nitaitdanin</i>		<i>ɣait</i>	<i>maitdici</i>	<i>khamait</i>				
	<i>nɪɣaitnɔɣ</i>	<i>khanɪɣaitden</i>	<i>nɪɣaitdaniminka</i>			<i>nitaitdanimin</i>		<i>nɪɣaitdin</i>	<i>nɪɣaitdincin</i>	<i>khanɪɣaitnin</i>				

Table 7. Transitive paradigm (past) of *itma* 'give'. Within the paradigm table, the upper cases refer to affirmative and the lower cases refer to negative. (Chintang and Puma Documentation Project 2008)

* The form I found in the original paradigm was equal to the negated form, probably due to a typo. So I slightly changed the form to the form of which I guess it may be right.

3.2.4 Compound Verbs

Sharma (2006) describes compound verbs in Puma. Compound verbs are an areal feature of South Asia. They are combinations of two verbs, whereas the first verb (V1) is the main verb, and the second verb (V2) is a vector verb. The vector verbs fulfill a telic, continuative or benefactive function. Causative and reflexive functions are realized by valency changing devices. In Kiranti languages, both verbs, V1 and V2, are inflected. Example (20) shows the verb *khamma* ‘put on stove’ in the V1 position and the verb *itma* ‘give’ as V2 expresses benefactive meaning.

(20) (Sharma 2006; [folk_tale_01.030 ff DR])

<i>tonpɔŋ=na</i>	<i>khiwama-cha</i>	<i>hekchakuwa-lai</i>	<i>unku</i>
then.after=TOP	a_person-ADD	a_person-DAT	small
<i>bucha-do</i>	<i>roj</i>	<i>khapd-i-itd-i=ni</i>	
earthenware.pot-GEN.LOC	rice	put.on.stove-3P-BEN-3P=REP	

‘Then for Hechkuwa, khiwama put the rice into a small pot and put it onto the stove.’

4 Ditransitives

4.1 The term ‘Ditransitive’

Malchukov et al. (forthcoming) define a ditransitive construction as a construction with an agent argument (A argument), a recipient-like argument (R argument) and a theme-like argument (T argument), where these semantic role labels are understood broadly.

Haspelmath (2004: 43) states that R arguments tend to be first or second person pronouns, proper names, animate and/or definite, whereas Themes tend to be third person full NPs, common nouns, inanimate and/or indefinite. He states that such tendency correlates with “greater and lesser topicworthiness” and generalizes towards a “Ditransitive Topicality-Role Constraint” (ibid.: 57). Discussing the Ditransitive Person Role Constraint, Haspelmath (2004: 56) gives two scales, the role scale (R > T) and the person scale (1, 2 > 3).

Typical ditransitive verbs are ‘give’, ‘sell’, ‘show’, ‘bring’, ‘teach’, ‘tell’, ‘feed’, ‘send’. Of them ‘give’ is the most frequent one. Typically, verbs of physical transfer describe an agent participant (the A argument), causing an object (the T argument) to physically transfer to an animate receiver (the R argument). Besides, verbs of mental transfer behave very similar to those of physical transfer.

Different ditransitive verbs of one language do not unavoidably behave the same way. Every language can have more than one ditransitive construction. Haspelmath (2005b) points out that ‘give’, the most frequent ditransitive verb in most languages, in English can occur within the Double-Object Construction (for example *Kim gave me a pen.*) and the Prepositional Object Construction (for example *Kim gave a pen to me.*).

If a language has several ditransitive constructions, for each construction the first question to be answered should be: Under which conditions is this construction used?

Malchukov et al. (forthcoming) assume a difference between ditransitive and benefactive constructions, as beneficiaries are possible also with intransitive verbs. Besides, they suggest extending the notion of ditransitives to derived ditransitives, such as causatives and applicatives of transitive verbs. As

the cause of such verbs often behaves like the R argument, they link it to the fact that “meanings of transfer verbs contain a ‘cause’ element”. But it is important to note that in their approach they exclude those derived ditransitives when they speak about *ditransitives*.

4.2 Major Ditransitive Alignment Types

Comparing encoding of transitive and ditransitive constructions cross-linguistically, Haspelmath (2005b) and Malchukov et al. (forthcoming) identify three major alignment types, namely

- (a) the indirective ($R \neq P = T$),
- (b) the neutral ($T = P = R$), and
- (c) the secundative ($R = P \neq T$) alignment types (see Figure 3).

Thus, in determining the alignment of a ditransitive construction one compares the encoding of the R and the T argument to the encoding of the monotransitive P argument.

Figure 3. Major Ditransitive Alignment Types (according to Haspelmath 2005b: 2; Malchukov et al. (forthcoming))

In the indirective alignment type, also known as indirect object alignment, the P and the T arguments behave alike but differently from the R argument. In the neutral alignment type, often called double object construction, all three arguments (P, T and R) behave alike. Finally, in the secundative alignment type, also known as secondary object alignment, the P and the R arguments behave alike, in contrast to the T argument, which behaves differently. The behavior of the A argument does not play a role here.

What are not considered here are the tripartite alignment type, where all arguments are treated differently, and the horizontal alignment type, where R

and T arguments are treated alike, but differently from P arguments. The reason for not taking these types into account is their rarity.

These three basic alignment types are distributed unevenly in the languages of the world. Haspelmath (2005b) states that when one considers flagging, indirective alignment is much more frequent than neutral alignment. Secundative alignment is even rarer. Considering indexing, in the vast majority of the languages ditransitive constructions are aligned neutrally. There are just a few languages with secundatively aligned ditransitive constructions, and even less with indirective alignment. However, this is just a tentative assumption, as Haspelmath's (2005b) language sample (with one or more constructions per language) is rather small. The project on *Ditransitive Constructions in the World's Languages* aims to achieve a broader survey about the distribution of these basic alignment types among the languages of the world.

Moreover Haspelmath (2005b: 5 f.) notes that ditransitive alignment is independent from the monotransitive alignment type one finds in a language.

4.3 Coding Properties: Flagging, Indexing, Word Order, and beyond

When Malchukov et al. (forthcoming) speak about alignment, the coding properties to determine the alignment are flagging, indexing and word order. Speaking about flagging, Malchukov et al. (forthcoming) mean case or adpositional marking of the arguments. Under the term indexing they subsume person (-number) cross-referencing or agreement.

Furthermore, the word order plays a role in alignment. Mostly, both R and T arguments appear on the same side of the word. Thus, it is interesting when T and the R arguments appear on different sides with respect to the verb. If both arguments appear on the same side of a verb, the word order with respect to each other is to investigate.

Malchukov et al. (forthcoming) assume flagging to be “more sensitive to role properties”, indexing “more sensitive to inherent prominence (animacy, definiteness)”. This leads to the assumption that P arguments and T arguments are treated alike because both are undergoers. P arguments and R arguments are treated alike because both can, in contrast to T arguments, be.

Moreover, behavioral properties of ditransitive constructions, as inter alia Passivization, Antipassivization, Relativization, Constituent questions,

Reflexivization, Reciprocalization, and Nominalization shall be investigated. The question is which of the R / T arguments can undergo these processes, thus, if these arguments behave alike or differently from the P argument of a monotransitive verb.

5 Ditransitives in Puma

Bickel (2007: 3) and Bickel and Nichols (2009: 306 ff.) (following the terminology of Dowty (1991) and others) state that there generally is a difference between a “more agent-like argument of a two-place predicate” and a “more agent-like argument of a three-place predicate” (Bickel & Nichols 2009: 306 ff.) But in the present work I will focus on the R and T argument, as I find no evidence to differentiate between the transitive and ditransitive A arguments in Puma.

Generally, the ditransitive alignment of Puma is secundative, like in other Southern Kiranti languages (cf. Bickel et al. 2007; Bickel 2007). “The O=G pattern seems to be etymologically linked to Proto-Tibeto-Burman” (Bickel 2007: 14).⁵ The secundative alignment is illustrated in the following examples. In the monotransitive examples (21) and (22), the P argument is optionally flagged by the DAT case *-lai* and is indexed on the verb by the suffix *-u/-i*. In the ditransitive examples (23) and (24) the R argument is obligatorily flagged by the dative case suffix *-lai* and indexed on the verb by the suffix *-i* and *-oŋ* respectively, the T argument is unflagged and not indexed on the verb.

(21) (Bickel et al. 2007: 6 f.)

<i>ŋa-a</i>	<i>yoni(-lai)</i>	<i>tup-u-ŋ.</i>
1SG-ERG	friend(-DAT)	meet-3SG.P-1SG.A

‘I met a/the/my friend.’

(22) *kΛ-ma-a* *kΛ-cha(-lai)* *qher(-i)-i.*
 3SG.POSS-mother-ERG 3SG.POSS-child(-DAT) beat(-PST)-3P
 ‘The mother beats(/beat) her child.’ [SKR 1.033]

(23) *Kamala-a* *Shree-lai* *bΛtuko[-Ø]* *itd-i.*
 a_person-ERG a_person-DAT a.bowl[-NOM] give-3R
 ‘Kamala gives Shree a bowl.’ [SKR 1.001]

(24) *khanna-a* *ŋa-lai* *Λk-ta kitaba[-Ø]* *t(Λ)-itd-oŋ.*
 2SG-ERG 1SG-DAT one-CLF book[-NOM] 2-give-1SG.R.PST
 ‘You (SG) gave me a book.’ [GKR 6.002]

As in the above examples, R and P arguments are treated alike, the alignment of flagging and indexing is secundative. In what follows, I will address the issue of how the R and T arguments behave while applying several syntactic tests.

⁵ In Malchukov et al.’s (forthcoming) terminology that is the P=R secundative alignment pattern.

5.1 The Dative Construction

Puma has more than one ditransitive construction. But it seems that the main, and probably most neutral and widespread ditransitive construction is a construction which is called *Dative Construction* here. In the dative construction the R argument obligatorily needs to be flagged by the dative case *-lai*. The following part focuses on the dative construction, but does not totally ignore other constructions. Characterizing the conditions under which one would expect the dative construction in Puma, one could say that it could occur in any neutral context. Interestingly, in contrast to Chintang (cf. Bickel et al. (forthcoming)), Puma seems to have no double object construction. Some few examples of one further construction, which I call *Alternative Construction*, appear within the present work. Characteristic for the alternative construction is the appearance of the (neutral) comitative 2 case suffix *-pado*.

5.2 Argument Coding Properties

The following schema shows the alignment properties in the dative construction. Thus, the basic constituent order is A R T V. The A argument is obligatorily flagged by the ergative case suffix, the R argument is obligatorily flagged by the dative case suffix, and the T argument remains unmarked. The indexing on the verb shows agreement with the A argument (if it is not a 3rd person singular A argument) and with the R argument.

The argument coding properties of the dative construction are overviewed in the following schema, and described in further detail in the following sections.

A-ERG	R-DAT	T-NOM[-Ø]	(A-)V(-A)-R
-------	-------	-----------	-------------

5.2.1 Flagging

Regarding case-marking in Puma, Bickel et al. (2007: 6) state that “with transitively inflected verb forms”, the A argument obligatorily bears the ergative marker. The P argument optionally bears the dative marker. Commenting on the fact that the dative case is optional with P arguments, Bickel et al. (2007: 6) state that “the odds for case marking are higher for human than non-human, animate than inanimate, and definite than indefinite

arguments – thus following a pattern roughly similar to well-known instances of differential object marking.”

The R argument of a ditransitive verb (which Bickel et al. (2007: 6) call “most goal-like argument”) is obligatorily flagged by the dative case suffix *-lai*. The T argument of a ditransitive verb (which Bickel et al. (2007: 6) call “least goal-like argument”) never bears the dative case *-lai*. The T argument is in the unmarked nominative case and thus unflagged.

monotransitive	ditransitive
A-ERG	A-ERG
P(-DAT)	R-DAT
	T-NOM

Table 8. Flagging of monotransitive and ditransitive arguments

The A argument of a monotransitive as well as of a ditransitive verb is flagged by the ergative case throughout. That is one evidence for the assumption that there is no formal difference between monotransitive and ditransitive A arguments in Puma. The S argument of an intransitive verb is in the nominative and thus zero marked. The same applies to the T argument of a ditransitive verb.

Considering the case marking of the R and T arguments with respect to case marking of P arguments, one sees that the P argument and the R argument are treated alike, while the T argument is marked differently. Thus, in terms of case marking, the dative construction shows secundative alignment.

These findings are attested in examples (25) a. and b. The monotransitive example (25) a. shows the A argument obligatorily flagged by the ergative case suffix *-a* and the P argument optionally flagged by the dative case suffix *-lai*. In the ditransitive example (25) b. the A argument is obligatorily flagged by the ergative case suffix *-a*, the R argument is obligatorily flagged by the dative case suffix *-lai* and the T argument is zero marked for the nominative case. When the T argument is flagged by the dative case suffix *-lai* the sentence is ungrammatical.

and the T argument is reversed. Here it is not A R T V anymore, but A T R V. The reasons of this change are discussed in § 5.2.3.

- (31) *khokku-a* *oku[-Ø]* *khokku-lai* *itd-i-i.*
 3SG-ERG 3SG[-NOM] 3SG-DAT give-PST-3R
 ‘She gave it to him.’ [SKR 1.006]

Thus, with regard to flagging the full noun phrase / independent personal pronoun distinction does not have an effect.

In this description of flagging within the dative construction, the fact that the dative case *-lai* on the P argument optionally might be omitted was ignored. Further investigation of the circumstances under which the dative case might be omitted needs to be done. Then one would need to compare the optional nominative flagging of the P argument, which is not flagged datively then, to the flagging of the R and T arguments of a ditransitive verb.

Finally, there is one exceptional ditransitive example. Example (32) would be acceptable without the dative case *-lai* on the R argument only in colloquial speech, but not in written or in formal speech. The reason might be that it is a derived ditransitive verb (monotransitive ‘see’-CAUS).

- (32) *ŋa-a* *uŋ-ma-un-pa-ci* *khanna-lai^l-Ø*
 1SG-ERG 1SG.POSS-mother-1SG.POSS-father-Du 2SG-DAT^l-NOM
khay-metd-na.
 see-CAUS-1SG>2
 ‘I showed my parents to you (SG).’ [KKR 9.001]/ [GKR 8.005]

5.2.2 Indexing

This section deals with the question of agreement or cross-referencing of the R and T arguments on the verb in comparison to the indexing of monotransitive P arguments.

In Puma, monotransitive verbs agree with A and P arguments. On ditransitive verbs the R argument, but not the T argument, triggers agreement. Thus, with regard to indexing the P and the R argument are treated alike. In other words, indexing is secundative.

To provide an overview of the agreement affixes, Table 9 which gives a “Simplified overview of alignment in agreement” (Schackow 2008: 17) is repeated.

In example (36), it is obvious as well that the R argument, but not the T argument is indexed on the verb. The R argument is in the 1st person singular pronoun and is indexed on the verb via a suffix.

(36)	<i>khanna-a</i>	<i>ŋa-lai</i>	<i>ak-ta</i>	<i>kitaba[-∅]</i>	<i>t(Λ)-itd-oy.</i>
	2SG-ERG	1SG-DAT	one-CLF	book[-NOM]	2-give-1SG.R.PST
	'You gave me a book.'				[GKR 6.002]

Also with regard to indexing the question arises whether the full NP/independent pronoun distinction has an effect. As one sees in example (37), there seems to be no effect on indexing. In this example just the word order is different.

(37)	<i>khokku-a</i>	<i>oku[-∅]</i>	<i>khokku-lai</i>	<i>itd-i-i.</i>	
	3SG-ERG	3SG[-NOM]	3SG-DAT	give-PST-3R	
	'She gave it to him.'				[SKR 1.006]

In example (38) is shown that the pronominal arguments can be dropped. Here the identity of the A and the R arguments is clear from the indexing on the verb.

(38)	<i>takku</i>	<i>bhasa[-∅]</i>	<i>kha-mΛ-itd-a</i>	
	DIST	language[-NOM]	1NSG.R-3PL.A-give-PST	
	'They gave us that language.'			[myth_puma_01.22]

Thus, the monotransitive P argument and the ditransitive R argument are treated alike, as distinguished from the T argument. So one can say that indexing shows secundative alignment.

5.2.3 The order of R and T

Malchukov et al. (forthcoming) state that it is most common in the languages of the world that the R and the T argument occur on the same side of the verb. This is also true for Puma. As one sees in example (39) below and (36) above, the neutral word order within the dative construction in Puma is as follows:

A-ERG R-DAT T(-∅) (A-)V(-A)-R

The A argument is followed by the R argument, which is followed by the T argument. Furthermore, the neutral word order is verb-final. One can say that the dominant word order is R > T.

	A	R	T	V
(39)	<i>Kamala-a</i>	<i>Shree-lai</i>	<i>baṭuko[-Ø]</i>	<i>itd-i.</i>
	a_person-ERG	a_person-DAT	a.bowl[-NOM]	give-3P
	‘Kamala gives Shree a bowl.’			[SKR 1.001]

But exceptions are allowed, as in examples (40) and (41), one sees the reversed word order of the R and the T argument⁸. Considering example (40) tempts to assume that the change in word order might be due to the fact that the R argument is not expressed by a full noun phrase but by a pronoun. However, this cannot be the case. Comparing example (36), one finds a pronominal R argument but the basic word order. Thus, example (40) gives rise to the conclusion that it may play a role that the T argument is animate, even human, and animacy may have an effect on word order.

	A	T	R	V
(40)	<i>khokku-a</i>	<i>cha[-Ø]</i>	<i>takku-ci-lai</i>	<i>itd-i-ci.</i>
	3SG-ERG	child[-NOM]	3SG-NSG-DAT	give-3R-NSG
	‘S/he gives the child to them (the aunts or some others).’			[GKR 8.014]

In (41) another example with reversed order of the R and the T argument is shown. Here neither the R argument nor the T argument are expressed by a full noun phrase, but are expressed by independent personal pronouns. This leads to the speculation whether it plays a role that both R and T arguments are expressed by pronouns. Another assumption might be that the change of the word order has to do with topicalization. But this is only speculation and needs to be verified systematically. Therefore, some further investigation on this question is necessary.

	A	T	R	V
(41)	<i>khokku-a</i>	<i>oku[-Ø]</i>	<i>khokku-lai</i>	<i>itd-i-i.</i>
	3SG-ERG	3SG[-NOM]	3SG-DAT	give-PST-3R
	‘She gave it to him.’			[SKR 1.006]

So the question arises, whether the appearance of a pronoun in place of the T argument, or in place of both, the R and T argument triggers a change of the word order, or whether other reasons need to be discovered.

⁸ The order of R and T with respect to A and V remains still the same.

5.2.4 Animacy (hierarchy) effects

In the Questionnaire on Ditransitive constructions, Comrie et al. (2007) furthermore ask, whether it is possible to construct ditransitive sentences with animate themes? If so, peculiarities need to be investigated.

In example (42) the human T argument *cha* ‘child’ appears. The fact that it is a human T argument does neither change flagging nor indexing. Though, it is remarkable that the word order of the R and the T arguments with respect to each other is reversed. That may be an effect of the humanness of the T argument.

- (42) *khokku-a cha[-Ø] takku-ci-lai itd-i-ci.*
 3SG-ERG child[-NOM] 3SG-NSG-DAT give-3R-NSG
 ‘S/he gives the child to them (the aunts or some others).’
 [GKR 8.014]

The same word order reversing of the R and T arguments is shown in the alternative construction example (43) with the verb *laɲma* ‘sell’. Very challenging is the fact that the flagging has changed. The A argument is flagged by the ergative case suffix, as one expects it. But, the R argument is now flagged by the comitative 2 suffix, and the T argument is flagged by the dative case suffix. Is this due to the animacy of the T argument?

- (43) *ka-pa-a ka-chetkumacha-lai Indian-pado*
 POSS-father-ERG 3SG.POSS-daughter-DAT Indian-COM2
laks-i.
 sell-3P/R
 ‘The father (man) sells his daughter to the Indian.’ [SKR 1.042a]

In (44) the word order is the same as in (43). But, the T argument is not flagged with the dative case suffix, but unmarked.

- (44) *khokku-a ka-cha[-Ø] indian-pado laks-i.*
 3SG-ERG 3SG.POSS-child[-NOM] Indian-COM2 sell-3P/R
 ‘He (the man) sells his daughter to the Indian.’ [GKR 8.007]

These are interesting findings which lead to the question, whether the dative case marking on the T argument is not obligatory, but optional. That leads to the assumption that the “T argument” in the two examples (43) and (44) are not T but P arguments, thus optionally flagged by the dative case suffix. Furthermore, this would result in the assumption, that the “R argument” in these two

examples is not an R argument but an adjunct. Thus, the verb *laɣma* ‘sell’ and the alternative construction might not be ditransitive.

5.2.5 *Interaction between coding strategies*

Additionally, it is of interest whether different coding strategies interact with each other, and if they do so how then the interaction takes place. As already discussed in the above sections on flagging, indexing, and the order of R and T arguments, there is no strong evidence for the interaction between coding strategies so far.

5.3 Behavioral Properties

In the following sections I address the issue of behavioral properties under different syntactic circumstances in Puma in general and especially with ditransitives. § 5.3.1 and subsections deal with different strategies for relative clause formation. § 5.3.2 deals with focusing, § 5.3.3 is concerned with constituent questions, § 5.3.4 deals with reflexivization. In § 5.3.5 reciprocalization is described. Finally, § 5.3.6 and subsections deal with antipassivization

5.3.1 *Relative Clause Formation*

This section deals with the question, which arguments can be relativized on, and how the relativization is realized.

In Puma, relativization is realized through nominalization of the verb. Within the relative clause the position of the verbal head is final. The relative clause precedes its antecedent. In their tentative findings on relativization in Puma, Bickel et al. (2006) state that there are some participles, formed by means of different affixes and clitics, which are used to express relativization⁹. In the following § 5.3.1.1 relativization via the active participle is described, § 5.3.1.2 deals with the obligative relativization, and § 5.3.1.3 deals with locative relativization, and § 5.3.1.4 gives an account of the relativization through the nominalizer =ku.

5.3.1.1 *Relativization via Active Participle*

According to Bickel et al. (2006), the prefix *ka-*, optionally combined with nominalization suffixes (*-pa* (masculine) / *-ma* (feminine)), nominalizes the verb and thus, builds the active participle. It is neither marked for tense, nor for person. This way of expressing relativization is most likely for human referents. But as one sees in example (46), it is as well possible for non-human animates. Schackow (2008: 90) states that this kind of relativization “can be used for characteristic actions of referents, as well as spontaneously, to describe a particular situation”.

⁹ Bickel et al. (2006) point to the fact that it is not clear yet “whether these clitics require subjunctive mood as they do in Chintang or Belhare”.

pattern:

$k\lambda$ - Σ^{10} (-pa/-ma)
ACT.PTCP- Σ (-NMLZ.M/NMLZ.F)

applicable to:

human (or at least animate) S and A arguments

Bickel et al. (2006) provide examples which show that relativization with $k\lambda$ - is possible for human S arguments (cf. example (45) a.), as well as for human A arguments. In (45) b. and (45) c., one finds the relativization on a human A argument of a monotransitive and a ditransitive verb, respectively. For human P arguments the relativization with $k\lambda$ - is impossible, as one sees in the ungrammatical example (45) d:

(45) (Bickel et al. 2006)¹¹

- a. $[k\lambda$ -puŋ-pa/-ma] (manna) (human S)
ACT.PTCP-go-NMLZ.M/-NMLZ.F person
'the person who goes' / 'the goer'
- b. [uŋ-yoŋni-lai $k\lambda$ -dhe] manna (human A (tr.))
1SG.POSS-friend-DAT ACT.PTCP-beat person
'the person who beats my friend'
- c. [uŋ-yoŋni-lai kitap $k\lambda$ -it] manna (human A (ditr.))
1SG.POSS-friend-DAT book ACT.PTCP-give person
'the person who gave my friend a book'
- d. * [uŋ-yoŋni-a $k\lambda$ -dhe] manna (intended: P)
1SG.POSS-friend-ERG ACT.PTCP-beat person
Intended: 'the person whom my friend beats'

Example (46) shows the relativization on an animate (but not human) A argument.

(46) (Schackow 2008: 90)

- [wachelet $k\lambda$ -khek] khipa (animate A (tr.))
chick ACT.PTCP-bite dog
'the dog that bites the chick(s)'

¹⁰ The ' Σ ' indicates that the following affix directly attaches to the verb stem, which cannot be inflected any further.

¹¹ In the examples cited from Bickel et al. (2006) I added the glosses and partly the translations, thus potential mistakes are to be blamed to me.

To summarize, relativization via the active participle is possible for S and A arguments. The argument on which is to be relativized, follows the relative clause. Furthermore, it is to mention that antipassivization is possible. As the relativization via active participle is not applicable to P arguments, it is likely that it is not applicable to R or T arguments either. So the alignment with regard to the behavior of R and T as compared to P arguments in relativization via active participle might be neutral. But, as I do not have data which shows, whether it is really not possible to apply this kind of relativization to R or T arguments, further investigation needs to be done on this issue.

5.3.1.2 *Obligative Relativization*

Bickel et al. (2006) say that attaching the infinitive marker *-ma*¹² conjoint with the nominalizer *-pa* to the verb form causes obligative relativization. Obligative relativization cannot be applied to A and S arguments, but to P arguments, instruments, and locations (cf. as well Schackow 2008: 88 f.).

pattern:

Σ -*ma-pa*
 Σ -INF-NMLZ

applicable to:

P arguments, instruments, locations

In example (47), the obligative relativization of a P argument is shown.

- (47) (Bickel et al. 2006)
- | | | |
|---------------------------|--------------|-----|
| <i>[bu-ma-pa]</i> | <i>manna</i> | (P) |
| [call- INF-NMLZ] | person | |
| ‘the man we need to call’ | | |

In example (48), Schackow (2008) provides an example for obligative relativization of an instrument:

- (48) (Schackow 2008: 88)
- | | |
|---|--------------|
| <i>chap-ma-pa</i> | (instrument) |
| write- INF-NMLZ | |
| ‘something that has to be written with, pen etc.’ | |

¹² Schackow (2008: 88) states that “the bare infinitive is commonly used to express the obligation of an event”.

In example (49) the obligative relativization is expressed, referring to a location.

- (49) (Bickel et al. 2006)
- [*puŋ-ma-pa*] *khim* (location)
go-**INF-NMLZ** house
'the house which I need to go to'

In this section, the obligative relativization of P arguments, instruments and locations is discussed. One could expect that obligative relativization of the R as well as of the T arguments should be possible. Unfortunately, I did not encounter any data on these possibilities yet. Thus, some further investigation needs to be carried out on this issue.

5.3.1.3 Locative Relativization

According to Bickel et al. (2006), the locative nominalization clitic =*kha* is attached to the verb which is prefixed by a possessive marker. It is restricted to relativization on locations:

pattern:

POSS-V=*kha*
POSS-V=LOC.NMLZ

applicable to:

locations

Places of events can be specified. In example (50) the relativization results in a modifying participle.

- (50) (Schackow 2008: 89)
- [*en-kama-mu=kha*] *aphis* (location)
1PL.INCL.POSS-work-do=LOC.NMLZ office
'the office in which we work'

For the locative relativization one can speculate whether it would be applicable to R arguments, but this question is one of those which need to be further investigated.

5.3.1.4 The Attributive Clitic¹³ =ku

The clitic =ku serves as a general nominalizer. Bickel et al. (2006) tentatively suppose that this kind of relativization is applicable to non-human S and A arguments and to any kind of P argument. However, the examples below demonstrate a broader use. One can assume that the attributive clitic =ku can be used for the relativization of any argument, not only non-human but also human S and A arguments, and, furthermore, besides the relativization of P arguments, for the relativization of R and T arguments.

pattern:

V¹⁴=ku
V=NMLZ

applicable to:

S, A, P, R, and T arguments, locations

Bickel et al. (2006) provide the following examples, in which several arguments are relativized, by the attachment of the nominalizing clitic =ku to the inflected verb. In these examples there is the 3rd person P argument (and R argument, respectively) indexed on the verb. In example (51) a. a location is relativized. In example (51) b. a relativized human P argument is shown. In example (51) c. a non-human (but animate) P argument is relativized. Example (51) d. shows the relativization of a human A argument of the ditransitive verb *itma* ‘give’. In example (51) e. the R argument of *itma* is relativized, and in example (51) f. the (inanimate) T argument of *itma* is relativized, the R argument is dropped but indexed on the verb.

- (51) (Bickel et al. 2006)
- a. [puks-a-ku] khim (location)
go-PST=NMLZ house
‘the house he went to’
- b. [uŋ-yoŋni-a dher-i=ku] manna (human P)
1SG.POSS-friend-ERG beat-3P=NMLZ person
‘the person who my friend beat (up)’

¹³ The label “Attributive Clitic” for the nominalizer =ku is adopted from Schackow (2008: ff).

¹⁴ The ‘V’ indicates that the following affix attaches to an inflected verb, thus the following morpheme is a clitic.

Below one finds an example (53) with the verb *dotma* ‘beg, ask for’, which assigns the comitative 2 case to the R argument, but undergoes relativization in the same way dative construction verbs do.

- (53) [Kamala-a Shree-pado dot-i=**ku**] bʌʈuko... (T)
 a_person-ERG a_person-COM2 beg-3R=NMLZ a.bowl
 ‘The bowl, Kamala asks Shree for...’ [KR 4.006b]

In example (54), the T argument of the ditransitive verb *laŋma* ‘sell’ is relativized. Special about this verb is that in a basic (ditransitive) clause it appears with two different case frames, concerning the R argument (cf. examples (55) a. and b. below). The verb *laŋma* ‘sell’ assigns the dative case *-lai* or the comitative 2 case *-pado* to the R argument. In the following relativized example the R argument is flagged by the dative case *-lai*.

- (54) [dokane-a marcha-lai laks-i=**ku**] tit khoŋni-yaŋ.
 trader-ERG woman-DAT sell-3R=NMLZ cloth beautiful-IPFV
 ‘The cloth that the trader sold the woman is beautiful.’ [GKR 8.006]

The question arises, whether the example in (54) was grammatically correct if the R argument bears the comitative 2 case. Thus, also on the issue of case assignment within relative clauses, modifying R or T arguments, further research is inevitable.

To summarize, the attributive clitic *=ku* is used for relativization of both the R and the T argument of a ditransitive verb. This happens in the same way as relativization of the P argument of a monotransitive verb. Thus, with regard to relativization the alignment is neutral.

Even demoted (antipassivized) objects can be relativized on (cf. § 5.3.6). Furthermore, the nominalizer *=ku*, in its use as attributive clitic, is applicable to more than just relativization (for further details on its attachment to phrases and clauses cf. Schackow 2008: 93 ff.).

Summarizing the findings on relative clause formation in Puma, one can say that relativization in Puma is head-external and head-final. Thus, the head follows the relative clause. As for relativization of R and T arguments, the relativization via active participle (§ 5.3.1.1) seems to be impossible for R and T arguments. Obligative relativization (§ 5.3.1.2) of R and T arguments still needs

to be investigated, and it is not yet clear, whether locative relativization (§ 5.3.1.3) is applicable to R (or even T) arguments. § 5.3.1.4 shows that relativization of R and T arguments is possible with the clitic =*ku* and there seem to be no restrictions. It is striking that all the elicited relative clauses were realized via the attributive clitic =*ku*. The relativization strategy with the attributive clitic =*ku* seems to be the less restricted and the most widespread one. There is certainly much more to be said about relative clause formation, but that goes beyond the scope of this work.

What is secondarily interesting is that relativization of non-arguments like locations is possible with three of the four above-mentioned strategies, namely all but the active participle strategy (cf. examples (49), (50), and (51) a.).

5.3.2 Focusing

The question arises, whether focusing is a further strategy of realizing relativization. Intended during the elicitation was relativization. The outcome was the alternative construction examples (55) a. and b.

- (55) a. *takku tit pasale-a marcha-lai laks(-i)-i.*
 DEM cloth trader-ERG woman-DAT sell(-PST)-3R
 Intended: ‘The cloth that the trader sold the woman.’
 Alternative: ‘The trader sold the woman the cloth.’ [SKR 1.049a]
- b. *takku tit pasale-a marcha-pado laks(-i)-i.*
 DEM cloth trader-ERG woman-COM2 sell(-PST)-3R
 Intended: ‘The cloth that the trader sold the woman.’
 Alternative: ‘The trader sold the woman the cloth.’ [SKR 1.049b]

In the above examples the word order changed possibly due to focus. But that is just a preliminary assumption and has to be investigated in detail. It is noticeable that the “R argument” alternatively bears dative or comitative 2 case marking.

Example (56) with the verb *khutma* ‘bring to’ is a further example for focusing, realized through the change of the word order.

- (56) *takku ciya Kamala-a Shree-lai khutd(-i)-i...*
 DEM tea a_person-ERG a_person-DAT bring.to(-PST)-3P
 ‘The tea (that) Kamala brought Shree...’ [KKR 3.206a]

5.3.3 Constituent questions

A further question, Comrie et al. (2007), put in the questionnaire is, which arguments can be questioned in constituent questions.

Example (57) shows the question for the T argument. The interrogative pronoun appears, with respect to word order, in the place where the T argument appears in an affirmative clause. Flagging and indexing do not change. Example (58) shows the question for the R argument. Again, flagging and indexing do not change. The interrogative pronoun is flagged by the dative case suffix. Furthermore, it is now in the first position of the clause.

- (57) *Kamala-a Shree-lai doro itd-i?*
 a_person-ERG a_person-DAT **what** give-3R
 ‘What did Kamala give Shree?’ [SKR 1.021]
- (58) *sa-lai Kamala-a bʌtuko itd-i?*
who-DAT a_person-ERG a.bowl give-3R
 ‘Whom did Kamala give the book?’ [SKR 1.022]

There seem to be no restrictions. Both the R and T argument can be questioned.

5.3.4 Reflexivization

About reflexivization the question is raised, which arguments can serve as antecedent and target of reflexivization, and with respect to which other antecedents and targets it can appear (Comrie et al. 2007).

Ebert (1994: 52) states that in Kiranti languages reflexives and reciprocals “are sometimes expressed in the same way.”

For the Kiranti language Bantawa Rai (1985: 137 ff.) states that there exist no reflexive pronouns. Reflexivization is solely expressed by verbal marking. There are reflexive verb forms for 1st, 2nd, and 3rd person singular. Reflexivization with duals or plurals does not occur. He continues that for duals and plurals there are reciprocal forms available (see § 5.3.5). Ebert (1994: 52) continues that in Bantawa the reflexive form for the 1st person singular is marked by a reflexive and 1st person suffixes, whereas the 2nd and 3rd person forms share an invariable suffix.

In the Kiranti language Camling there are, in contrast to the situation in Bantawa, reflexive forms for not only singular but as well for dual and plural.

Again the 1st person singular form is different from the 2nd and 3rd person singular forms¹⁵. Furthermore, there is one reflexive form for all persons in the dual and plural (Ebert 1994: 52 f.; cf. also Ebert 1997a: 34). In the following example one sees the monotransitive verb ‘wash’ suffixed by the 1st person marker *-uŋ*, the reflexive suffix *-c* and again the 1st person suffix *-uŋa* (Ebert 1994: 52 ff.)

(59) Camling (NW dialect; Ebert 1994: 52)

hupd-uŋ-c-uŋa.

wash-1SG-REFL-1SG

‘I washed myself.’

Ebert (1994: 52) gives an example (60) of Limbu where the verb ‘give’ is marked by the prefix *mε-*, indexing the 3rd person plural A argument, and by the reflexive suffix *-siŋ* and the suffix *-ε*, indicating past tense.

(60) Limbu (Ebert 1994: 52)

mε-bi:-siŋ-ε.

3PL.A-give-REFL-PST

‘They (PL) gave to each other.’

Summarizing, Ebert (1994: 54) states that the reflexive marker in Kiranti languages might originate from a verb.

In the following the realization of reflexivization in Puma is illustrated.

In (61) reflexivization of the R argument is shown.

(61) *tʌku chetkumacha-a kʌnʌŋwa losum khay-metd-a-cen-a.*
 3SG girl-ERG new dress see-CAUS-PST-REFL-PST
 ‘The girl showed herself the new shirt.’ [GKR 2.115]

Here the A argument binds the reflexive. The reflexivization is realized through a compound. The 2nd verb fulfills grammatical function – here causative (*metd* – ‘do’) (cf. Schackow 2008: 14 f.)

¹⁵ There is another Camling dialect where all persons in the singular are marked the same way.

In the following example reflexivization of the R and T argument seems to happen

- (62) *Kamala-a khokku-a khokku-lai khaṅ-metd-a-cen-a.*
 a_person-ERG 3SG-ERG 3SG-DAT see-CAUS-PST-REFL-PST
 ('by her') ('to her')
- 'Kamala, she showed herself to herself.' (for example in the mirror)
 [GKR 2.117]

In the following example the T argument is reflexivized, the A argument binds the reflexive. The comitative 2 case suffix provokes the assumption that this could again be the alternative construction.

- (63) *taku chetkumacha-a ka-yoṅni-ṛado*
 3SG girl-ERG 3POSS-friend-COM2
khaṅ-metd-a-cen-a.
 see-CAUS-PST-REFL-PST
- 'The girl_i showed herself_i to (Kamala).' ('She_i lets her friend_j look at her(self)_i.')
- [GKR 2.116]

In the following example one finds a reflexive pronoun (borrowed from Nepali) and the reflexive marker on the verb. But strange is, that there is no overt case marking.

- (64) *Birgit aphaṅi Nepali cind-a-cen-a.*
 a_person REFL Nepali teach-PST-REFL-PST
- 'Birgit taught herself Nepali.'
 [KKR 3.145]

The following examples are elicited by Balthasar Bickel with Kamala Kumari Rai and Shree Kumar Rai and show that only R arguments can bind reflexives, T arguments cannot. The R arguments can be identified because they are obligatorily flagged by the dative case suffix *-lai*.

- (65) (Balthasar Bickel, p.c., elicited with Kamala Kumari Rai and Shree Kumar Rai)
- Prem-oṅ Ganesh-oṅ Joge-ṛado (*Joge-lai, *Joge-oṅ)*
 a_person-COM a_person-COM a_person-COM2 (*a_person-DAT, *a_person-COM)
- sin ṛa-metd-a-cen-a-ci*
 know 3S/A-make.do-PST-REFL-PST-3NSG.P
- 'Prem and Ganesh introduced themselves to Joge.'

- (66) (Balthasar Bickel, p.c., elicited with Kamala Kumari Rai and Shree Kumar Rai)
- a. *tʌ-khaŋ-nen-cen*
2-see-2SG.REFL-REFL
'You see yourself.'
- b. *tʌ-khaŋ-a-cen-a*
2-see-PST-REFL-PST
'You saw yourself.'
- c. *Prema Ganeshlai kʌ-chetkucha(*-lai) khaŋ*
a_person-ERG a_person-DAT 3SG.POSS-girl/daughter(*-DAT) see
metdi
make.do-3P
'He showed it to him.'
- d. *Prem-a Ganesh-lai ʌina-do khaŋ-men-cen metd-i*
a_person-ERG a_person-DAT mirror-GEN.LOC see-do-REFL make.do-3P
'Prem showed Ganesh to himself in the mirror.'
- e. **Prem-a Ganesh ʌina-do khaŋ-men-cen*
a_person-ERG a_person mirror-GEN.LOC see-do-REFL
metdi
do-3P
Intended: 'Prem showed Ganesh to himself in the mirror.'

5.3.5 Reciprocals

In their questionnaire, Comrie et al. (2007) raise the question, which arguments can serve as antecedent and target of reciprocal constructions, and with respect to which other antecedents and targets they can do so.

For the Kiranti language Bantawa Rai (1985: 137 ff.) states that there occur reciprocal verb forms for duals and plurals, but not for singular¹⁶ (see § 5.3.5). Summarizing the situation across the Kiranti languages, Ebert (1994: 52 ff.) states that reciprocity is often expressed like reflexivity. But in Athpare and Bantawa reciprocity is realized in a different way. As one sees in example (67) in Bantawa the verb is suffixed by the active participle *-pa* and followed by the verb *mɪ* 'do', which bears the inflection.

¹⁶ Cf. § 5.3.4 for reflexivization in Bantawa with 1st, 2nd, and 3rd person singular.

(67) Bantawa (Ebert 1994: 54)

dhat-pa ti-mi-a-nin.
beat-ACT.PTCP 2-do-PST-2PL

‘You (PL) beat (PST) each other.’

In (68) and (69), the R argument is reciprocalized.

(68) *Kamala-oy Shree-oy kitaba it pA-mu-a-ci.*
a_person-COM a_person-COM book give 3S/A-do-PST-DU.P
‘Kamala and Shree gave their books to each other.’ [SKR 1.029a]

(69) *khokku-ci kitaba it pA-mu-a-ci.*
3SG-NSG book give 3S/A-do-PST-DU.P
‘They gave their books to each other.’ [SKR 1.030a]

Reciprocalization of the T argument (A causes B & C to know each other) is demonstrated in the following examples.

(70) a. *Kamala-oy Shree-oy Ganesh-lai khay-met*
a_person-COM a_person-COM a_person-DAT see-CAUS
pA-mu-a-ci.
3S/A-do-PST-DU.P
‘Kamala and Shree showed each other to Ganesh.’ (DU)
[SKR 1.032a]

b. *Kamala-oy Shree-oy Ganesh-pado khay-met*
a_person-COM a_person-COM a_person-COM2 see-CAUS
pA-mu-a-ci.
3S/A-do-PST-DU.P
‘Kamala and Shree showed each other to Ganesh.’
[SKR 1.032b]

(71) (Balthasar Bickel, p.c., elicited with Kamala Kumari Rai & Shree Kumar Rai)

a. *Prem-oy Ganesh-oy khay pA-mu-a-ci.*
a_person-COM a_person-COM see 3A-AUX.RECP-PST-DU
‘Prem and Ganesh saw each other.’

b. *Prem-oy Ganesh-oy kAlAm[-Ø] it pA-mu-a-ci.*
a_person-COM a_person-COM pen[-NOM] give 3A-AUX.RECP-PST-DU
‘Prem and Ganesh gave each other a pen.’

- c. *Prem-oy* *Ganesh-oy* *Joge-pado* (**Joge-lai*, **Joge-oy*)
a_person-COM a_person-COM a_person-COM2(*a_person-DAT,*a_person-COM)
sin *met* *pa-mu-a-ci*.
know do 3A-AUX.RECP-PST-DU
‘Prem and Ganesh introduced each other to Joge.’

In examples (71) a-c, one finds reciprocal examples. In example (71) a., there is the monotransitive verb *khaṅma*¹⁷ ‘see’. The P argument is reciprocalized with the A arguments as the antecedent. The reciprocal meaning is expressed by marking the two A arguments with the comitative case suffix *-oy*, and, furthermore, an auxiliary construction. The verb itself is not inflected, and followed by the auxiliary *muma* ‘do’, which is grammaticalized for expressing reciprocalization. On the reciprocal auxiliary one finds the 3rd person A (or S) prefix *pa-* and the dual suffix *-ci*, referring to the two arguments.

In example (71) b. with the ditransitive verb *itma* ‘give’ one finds the reciprocalization of the R argument with the A arguments as antecedent. As in the monotransitive example (71) a. the two A arguments are both marked comitatively with the suffix *-oy* and the (plain) verb is followed by the reciprocal auxiliary *muma* which bears the 3rd person A marker, as well as the past tense marker and the dual suffix which refers to the two A arguments. Furthermore, one finds the unmarked / nominatively marked T argument *kalam* ‘pen’, which is not indexed on the verb.

In Example (71) c., the T argument is reciprocalized with the A arguments as the antecedent. But the construction with the derived ditransitive verb *sin met* ‘to introduce sb. to sb., to let sb. know sb.’ is another one. For now in the context of this work the construction will be called Alternative Construction. In this example the T argument is reciprocalized with the A arguments as antecedent. As in the examples (71) a. and b. the reciprocalization is realized through flagging the A arguments with the comitative case and complementing the verb with the reciprocal auxiliary. The auxiliary bears the 3rd person A marker, as well as the past tense marker and the dual suffix which refers to the two A arguments. Furthermore, there is the R argument which is flagged with the comitative 2 *-pado*. If the R argument was flagged with the comitative (1) case suffix *-oy* or the dative case suffix *-lai*, the

¹⁷ *khaṅma* is the citation form of the verb *khaṅ* ‘to see’. *-ma* is the infinitive marker.

example would be ungrammatical. So this construction differs from the Dative Construction in the case marking of the R argument (cf. example (72)).

- (72) (Balthasar Bickel, p.c., elicited with Kamala Kumari Rai & Shree Kumar Rai)

*Prem-oy Ganesh-oy Joge-pado (*Joge-lai, *Joge-oy)*
 a_person-COM a_person-COM a_person-COM2 (*a_person-DAT, *a_person-COM)
sin pa-metd-a-cen-a-ci
 know 3S/A-CAUS(make.do)-PST-REFL-PST-3NSG.P
 ‘Prem and Ganesh introduced themselves to Joge.’

In the following examples (73) a. and b. one finds the typical reciprocal construction. The appearance of the comitative case together with the auxiliary construction with the grammaticalized reciprocal auxiliary *mu* forms the reciprocal construction. The difference between the two examples is that in (73) a. one finds the comitative 1, in (73) b. one finds the comitative 2. For the difference between comitative 1 and comitative 2 see § 3.2.

- (73) (Balthasar Bickel, p.c., elicited with Kamala Kumari Rai & Shree Kumar Rai)

a. [*Joge-a [Prem-oy Ganesh-oy sin mu]*
 a_person-ERG a_person-COM a_person-COM know AUX.RECP
metd(-i)-i-ci.
 make.do(-PST)-3P-3NSG.P
 ‘Joge introduced Ganesh and Prem to each other.’

It is important to note, that the comitative case suffix *-oy* is obligatory here.

b. *Joge-a Prem-pado Ganesh-pado sin mu*
 a_person-ERG a_person-COM2 a_person-COM2 know AUX.RECP
metd(-i)-i-ci.
 make.do(-PST)-3P-3NSG.P
 ‘Jogo introduced Ganesh and Prem to each other.’

5.3.6 Antipassive

About the “syntax and morphology of antipassives” in Puma Bickel & Gaenzle (2005) state that one finds a similar situation like in other Kiranti languages. The antipassive verb bears intransitive agreement morphology and assigns case intransitively (i.e. nominative to S (demotedA)). Interesting is that in Puma there are two forms of antipassives – the *kha-* antipassive for human undergoers and the unmarked antipassive for nonhuman undergoers.

About the semantics of antipassives one can say that while the active sentence expresses a concrete action, the antipassivized sentence rather expresses a general activity. Furthermore, the antipassive is used for the expression of generic undergoers, nonspecific (referential) undergoers, and nonreferential undergoers (cf. Bickel & Gaenszle 2005). In the following example (74) with the verb *itma* ‘give’ a nonreferential undergoer is expressed.

- (74) (Bickel & Gaenszle 2005; [LH_M.124])
akwada *kaphakwa=cha kha-pa-it-nin=ku* *min-oy.*
 ever money=ADD ANTIP-NEG-give-NEG[NPST]=NMLZ think-1SG.S.PST
 ‘I thought he would never even give money to anyone.’

Compared to antipassivization of monotonatives the question is, which of the ditransitive arguments may undergo antipassivization, the R or the T argument.

For ditransitive verbs there are two ways of antipassivization, which Bickel et al. (2007) call incorporation and object omission respectively. In the following § 5.3.6.1 and § 5.3.6.2, respectively, these phenomena are described. Speaking about antipassivization in Puma, Bickel & Gaenszle (2005) state that objects are “accessible targets of relativization (unlike classical incorporates)”.

- (75) (Bickel et al. 2006)
uŋ-yojni *kha-qher-a-ku* *manna* (human P, ANTIP)
 1SG.POSS-friend ANTIP-beat-PST-NMLZ person
 ‘the kind of man that my friend would beat (in the past)’

5.3.6.1 Incorporation (Unmarked Antipassive)

Puma has an unmarked antipassive construction, also called “Ø-detransitivization” by Bickel et al. (2007), what is similar to idealized incorporation in that the incorporated object has nonspecific meaning and does not trigger object agreement. The S (demoted A) argument is marked by the nominative case rather than by the ergative case (cf. examples (76) a. and (77) b.). The incorporated object retains positional freedom and can be modified by adjectives. Furthermore, the obligatory object cannot be marked by the dative case.

The unmarked antipassive in Puma has “similar properties as in other Kiranti languages”. What is different to findings in other languages is that it is restricted to non-human objects (cf. Bickel & Gaenszle 2005).

This kind of detransitivization is possible only with the T argument of ditransitives (in contrast to the *kha-* antipassive, where only the R argument can be omitted; cf. § 5.3.6.2).

In example (76) b. one sees that the object is obligatory – when it is lacking the sentence is ungrammatical. In the monotransitive example (77) a. the pronominal (1st person) A argument is dropped, the 3rd person P argument *khim* ‘house’ is optionally flagged by the dative case *-lai*, and both arguments are indexed on the monotransitive verb *copma* ‘see’ (in contrast to the unmarked antipassive example in (77) b.).

(76) (Bickel et al. 2007: 7)

a. *ŋa[-∅]* *reŋio en-ŋa.*
1SG[-NOM] radio hear-1SG.S

‘I do radio-hearing.’ (in general, not relating to a specific radio)

b. **ŋa[-∅]* *en-ŋa.*
1SG[-NOM] hear-1SG.S.NPST

Intended: ‘I hear something.’

(77) (Bickel & Gaenszle 2005: 2)

a. *khim(-lai)* *copt-u-ŋ.*
house-DAT see-3P-1SGA

‘I see the house.’

b. *khim(*-lai)* *cop-ŋa.*
house(-DAT) see-1SG.S

‘I see houses.’

Furthermore, Bickel & Gaenszle (2005) state that in some respects the incorporated object behaves differently from classical incorporates. The object does not have to stand immediately next to the verb; it can be modified by adjectives. Moreover it can be the target of relativization.

In the following examples (78) a.-c. unmarked antipassivization of a ditransitive T argument is shown (cf. as well Bickel et al. 2007). In the ditransitive example (78) a. one finds the verb *itma* ‘give’ on which the 3rd person R argument and the 1st person singular A argument (which is dropped in the sentence) are indexed. The R argument *gai* ‘cow’ is obligatorily flagged by the dative *-lai* and the T argument *ghasa* ‘grass’ remains unmarked / in the nominative case. In example (78) b. one finds the unmarked antipassive

structure, antipassivizing the T argument: the verb is indexed intransitively for the 1st person S (demoted A) argument, the T argument is demoted and obligatorily has to appear, and the R argument remains, still flagged with the dative case. In example (78) c. one sees that it is ungrammatical to antipassivize the R argument (and remain the T argument (both unflagged) this way).

- (78) (Bickel & Gaenszle 2005: 2)
- a. *gai-lai* *ghasa[-∅]* *itd-u-u-η.*
 cow-DAT grass[-NOM] give-PST-3R-1SG.A
 ‘I gave the cow grass.’
- b. *gai-lai* *ghasa[-∅]* *itd-oj.*
 cow-DAT grass[-NOM] give-1SG.S.PST
 ‘I gave grass to the cow.’
- c. **ghasa[-∅]* *gai[-∅]* *itd-oj.*
 grass[-NOM] cow[-NOM] give-1SG.S.PST
 Intended: ‘I gave cows grass.’

As demonstrated above, only monotransitive P arguments and ditransitive T arguments can undergo the unmarked antipassivization. Unmarked antipassivization of the R argument is not possible. Thus, with respect to unmarked antipassivization in Puma the P argument is aligned with the T argument, alignment is indirective here. This contrasts to non-detransitized clauses, where the alignment is secundative (P and R are treated alike) (cf. Bickel et al. 2007: 9).

This contrasts with another kind of detransitivization, where only the R argument can be omitted. Object Omission (*kha-* antipassive) is described in the following § 5.3.6.2.

5.3.6.2 Object Omission (*kha-* Antipassive¹⁸)

Unlike the unmarked antipassive, the *kha-* antipassive is restricted to human objects. Furthermore, the P argument is obligatorily omitted and is assumed to be a human object with an existential reading. The *kha-* antipassive is also called “*kha-* detransitivization” (cf. Bickel & Gaenszle 2005; Bickel et al. 2007).

¹⁸ For the diachrony of *kha-* in the Kiranti languages (towards generic P > nonspecific referential P > nonreferential P antipassive and 1NSG.P agreement, respectively) cf. Bickel & Gaenszle 2005.

Speaking about “Antipassives for first person object reference in Puma”, Bickel & Gaenszle (2005) state that the prefix *kha*⁻¹⁹ is not only used for indexing the 1st person object (1P) on the verb, but – appearing together with intransitive agreement inflection – also for marking antipassives. The prefix *kha* detransitivizes the verb and qualifies it to have generic objects (cf. examples (79) a. and b.). They point out that this “constellation is extremely unusual in the languages of the world: wherever diathesis has been reported to develop into 1P marking, it involves a passive, not an antipassive” (Bickel & Gaenszle 2005).

(79) (Bickel & Gaenszle 2005: 1)

a. *en-i.*

hear-3P[PST]

(Active transitive inflection)

‘S/he heard him/her/it.’ (entails a specific undergoer referent)

b. *kha-en-a.*

ANTIP-hear-PST

(Antipassive intransitive inflection)

‘S/he heard someone / people.’ or ‘S/he listened so as to find out whether or not there are people.’ (does not entail existence of a specific undergoer referent) OR: ‘S/he heard us (incl.)’

Bickel et al. (2005b: 2 f.) give a list of 24 Puma verbs which so far have been found with the antipassive prefix *kha*-. Moreover the antipassive form is identical with forms with a 1st person non-singular P argument, as is demonstrated in example (80).

(80) (Bickel et al. 2005b: 3)

som-kha-ta-tuk

love-ANTIP-2-love.NPST

‘You love someone’ or ‘You love us.’

The following examples (81) a. & b. show the active and the *kha*- antipassivized with the monotransitive verb *somtukma* ‘love’.

(81) (Bickel et al. 2005b: 2)

a. *ŋa-a* *marcha-lai* *som-tukd-u-ŋ.*

1SG-ERG

girl-DAT

love-love.NPST-3SG.P-1SG.A

‘I love the / a (specific) girl.’

¹⁹ For the role of the prefix *kha*- in inverse replacement in Southeastern Camling cf. Ebert 1997: 22 ff.

- b. *ŋa[-∅]* *marcha-lai* *som-kha—tuk-ŋa.*
 1SG[-NOM] girl-DAT love-**ANTIP**-love.NPST-1SG.S
 ‘I love girls (in general).’

In example (81) a. the A-argument is flagged by the ergative case *-a*, the P-argument is flagged by the dative case *-lai*, and both are indexed on the verb through suffixes. In example (81) b. on the verb appears the antipassive marker *kha-*. The former A-argument has changed to an unflagged S-argument²⁰. On the verb there is only indexing for the S-argument. So the ‘girl’ is no argument anymore in this clause. The reference is generic.

In the monotransitive example (82) a. the A argument is flagged ergatively, the P argument is flagged datively, and both are indexed on the verb. In the antipassivized example (82) b. the verb is prefixed by *kha-*, the object is obligatorily omitted and is understood as a human object with an existential reading (“I hear people”)²¹.

- (82) (Bickel et al. 2007: 9)
- a. *ŋa-a* *kho-lai* *enn-u-ŋ.*
 1SG-ERG 3SG-DAT hear.NPST-3SG.P-1SG.A
 ‘I hear him/her.’
- b. *ŋa[-∅]* (**kho(-lai)*/**tokku(-lai)*/**manna(-lai)*/**baja(-lai)*)
 1SG[-**NOM**] 3SG(-DAT) DEM(-DAT) person(-DAT) song(-DAT)
 kha-en-ŋa.
 ANTIP-hear-1SG.S.NPST
 ‘I hear someone/people.’ *not*: * ‘I hear something.’

Bickel & Gaenszle (2005) state that, in contrast to the situation in the unmarked antipassive, the P argument cannot be the target of relativization²².

When the prefix *kha-* is applied to a ditransitive verb, it is the R argument that can and must be omitted. T arguments cannot undergo the *kha-* antipassivization. Comparing the ditransitive example (83) a. with the verb *itma* ‘give’ to the *kha-* antipassivized example (83) b. one sees that the R argument is omitted. The verb is marked by the antipassive marker *kha-* and,

²⁰ One could (rather) say that the argument is marked through the *-∅* marked nominative case.

²¹ Cf. example (76) a. in § 5.3.6.1 above, where the non-human P argument undergoes unmarked antipassivization with the same verb (*enma* ‘hear, listen’).

²² Relativization on *kha-* antipassivized object is impossible “because **kha* was quasi-incorporated and this made it inaccessible to syntactic operations” (Bickel & Gaenszle 2005: 4).

furthermore, the (dropped) 1st person S argument is indexed on the verb. In the ungrammatical example (83) c. it is demonstrated that *kha*- antipassivization is not applicable to T arguments.

- (83) (Bickel et al. 2007: 10)
- a. *yoỹni-lai* *cetkuma[-∅]* *itd-u-u-ŋ.*
 friend-DAT clan.sister[-NOM] give-PST-3P-1SG.A
 ‘I gave my celi (clan sister) to a friend (in marriage)’
- b. *chetkuma[-∅]* ***kha-itd-oỹ.***
 clan.sister[-NOM] **ANTIP-give-1sS.PST**
 ‘I gave away my sister (to someone/people).’
- c. **yoỹni(-lai)* ***kha-itd-oỹ.***
 friend(-DAT) **ANTIP-give-1sS.PST**
Intended: ‘I gave someone/people/some sister to a friend.’

Thus, with respect to *kha*- antipassivization in Puma the P argument is aligned with the R argument, so alignment is secundative here.

Schackow (2008: 90 f.) states that it is possible to antipassivize relativized (via active participle, cf. § 5.3.1.1) forms and provides the following example (84) with the monotransitive verb *q̃hema* ‘beat’:

- (84) (Schackow 2008: 91)
- kha-ka-q̃he-pa*** (human S)
ANTIP-ACT.PTCP-beat-NMLZ.M
 ‘someone who beats people’

6 Conclusion

For now the conclusion can be drawn that the main ditransitive construction in Puma is the Dative Construction, on which I focussed in the present work. The argument coding properties can be summarized in the following schema:

A-ERG R-DAT T-NOM[-Ø] (A-)V(-A)-R

At a first glance, the verb forms of the ditransitive verb *itma* 'give' do not differ from the verbal forms, which one finds in the monotransitive paradigm for *itma* 'give'. What is so interesting about the verbal agreement is to figure out with which arguments the verb agrees. In the case of the Puma Dative Construction the verb agrees with the A argument and with the R argument (just as monotransitive verbs agree with A and P arguments), but not with the T argument. Thus, alignment of indexing is secundative.

About flagging is to say, that in a basic ditransitive clause the A argument is flagged by the ergative case suffix, the R argument is flagged by the dative case suffix, and the T argument is zero marked (as compared to the monotransitive situation: A-ERG, P-DAT). Thus, alignment of flagging is secundative as well. As already mentioned in § 5.2.1, further investigation of the circumstances under which the dative case on P might be omitted needs to be done. Then one would need to compare the optional nominative flagging of the P argument, which is not flagged datively then, to the flagging of the R and T arguments of a ditransitive verb.

The dominant order of R and T is that R precedes the T argument, but variation is possible. There are probably animacy (hierarchy) effects, as one can see on dative construction examples, but as well on alternative construction examples. Up to now I found no clear evidence for the interaction between coding strategies.

For the behavioral properties it is to summarize that there are four different ways of realizing relative clause formation in Puma. But only for one of these I found ditransitive data - the Attributive Clitic =*ku* strategy. In this strategy the R and T arguments are treated equally. Thus, as for relativization, alignment is neutral here. Further investigation is inevitable to find out,

whether relative clause formation on R and T arguments is possible as well in the other three strategies. Furthermore, it needs to be mentioned that focusing influences the word order.

In constituent questions it is interesting to see, that when asking for the T argument, the interrogative pronoun appears in the position, where one finds the T argument in an affirmative clause. While asking for the R argument, the interrogative pronoun appears in the first position of the clause.

About reflexivization it is to be said that only R arguments can bind reflexives. Reciprocalization is interesting, because it is realized through attaching the comitative case suffix *-oŋ* and adding a reciprocal auxiliary which follows the verb. A very interesting finding in Puma is that there are two ways of antipassivization, one strategy for R and a different strategy for T arguments.

As this is only a first slight overview of how exciting ditransitives in Puma are, there is to be done a lot more research on this topic. Besides the above mentioned, there needs to be investigated on possible split-ergativity (cf. Bickel et al. (forthcoming) on Chintang and Belhare), motion verbs and their behavior, derived ditransitives, and the systematical distribution of the case suffixes *-pado* and *-lai*.

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Zusammenfassung

Die vorliegende Magisterarbeit behandelt *Ditransitives in Puma* (Ditransitiva im Puma). Puma ist eine vom Aussterben bedrohte Kiranti Sprache, die in den Ausläufern des Himalayas in Ostnepal gesprochen wird. Es gibt nur noch etwa 6000 Sprecher und die Sprache wird mehr und mehr von ihren Nachbarsprachen verdrängt. Darüberhinaus ist sie bisher kaum beschrieben. Dies hat sich jedoch geändert, seit sich das *Chintang and Puma Documentation Project* (Universität Leipzig und Tribhuvan Universität Kathmandu) mit der Dokumentation der Sprache Puma und einer seiner Nachbarsprachen, dem Chintang, beschäftigt.

Im Rahmen eines Praktikums innerhalb des *Chintang and Puma Documentation Projects* konnte ich mit Muttersprachlern des Puma zusammenarbeiten und Sprachdaten zum bisher für die Sprache Puma nahezu undokumentierten Bereich der Ditransitiva sammeln. Dies gelang auf der Grundlage des *Questionnaire on Ditransitive Constructions* (Fragebogen zu Ditransitivkonstruktionen), der innerhalb des Projekts zu *Ditransitivkonstruktionen in den Sprachen der Welt* (Max Planck Institut für Evolutionäre Anthropologie, Leipzig) entwickelt wurde.

In der vorliegenden Magisterarbeit sind einige wichtige Charakteristika der Grammatik des Puma zusammengefasst und darüberhinaus die Ergebnisse der Feldforschung zu Ditransitiva dargelegt und ausgewertet.

Einige wenige Fakten sind, dass die Dativkonstruktion eine grundlegende Wortstellung von Agens, Rezipient, Thema, Verb aufweist. Der Agens wird durch den Ergativkasus markiert, der Rezipient wird durch den Dativkasus markiert und das Thema ist unmarkiert, steht also im Nominativ. Am Verb findet man Kongruenz mit dem Agens und dem Rezipienten. Vergleicht man diese Resultate mit der Wortstellung, der Kasusverteilung und der Kongruenz monotontransitiver Konstruktionen, ergibt sich das Bild einer sekundativen Aliniierung. Ein weiterer spannender Aspekt ist, dass das Puma zwei Strategien hat, um Antipassivkonstruktionen zu bilden.

Erklärung

a)

Ich bin damit einverstanden, dass meine Masterarbeit in der Bibliothek öffentlich eingesehen werden kann. Die Urheberrechte müssen gewahrt bleiben. Die Arbeit enthält keine personenbezogenen Daten.

27.01.2009

b)

Hiermit versichere ich, dass ich die Arbeit in allen Teilen selbständig verfasst und keine anderen als die angegebenen Hilfsmittel benutzt habe.

27.01.2009